

Silhouette species list

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This supplement lists all species recorded as breeding, or suspected to breed, on Silhouette island. Only terrestrial, fresh-water and estuarine species are listed. For plants the lists includes species growing wild, this includes some non-reproductive individuals that are remnants of old cultivation. For all species the distribution outside the central (granitics plus Bird and Denis) islands of Seychelles is summarised with the following abbreviations:

End. = endemic	Ald. = Aldabra
Ami. = Amirantes	Masc. = Mascarenes
Mad. = Madagascar	Com. = Comoros
Afr. = Africa	Palaeotrop. = Palaeotropics
Pantrop = Pantropical	Cosmo. = Cosmopolitan

The Seychelles islands on which they have been recorded are listed in the standard order of islands used in other *Phelsuma* publications:

M. = Mahé	SA. = St. Anne	Cerf	Moy. = Moyenne
Long	Cach. = Cahée	Anon. = Anonyme	Rd. = Round (Mahé)
Sou. = Souris	Isl. = Islette	Con. = Conception	Ther. = Thérèse
Sil. = Silhouette	N. = North	P. = Praslin	Cur. = Curieuse
CS. = Chauve Souris	R. = Round (Praslin)	Co. = Cousin	Coe. = Cousine
A. = Aride	Coco. = Cocos	GS. = Grande Soeur	PS. = Petite Soeur
Alb. = Albatross	Fel. = Felicité	Mar. = Marianne	L.D. = La Digue
F. = Frogate	Bird	Denis	

Only references to Silhouette records are cited. These are the first references to specimens or observations, the aim of this publication is to summarise specific records and not to list all citations. Many new records are listed, where possible reference has been made to specimens held in the following museum collections:

MRAC = Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale, Tervuren, Belgium

MZT = Zoological Museum of Turku University, Finland

NPTS = The Nature Protection Trust of Seychelles

Species and families are listed in a standard order if a recent monographic treatment is available, otherwise all taxa are listed alphabetically.

PLANTAE

BRYOPHYTA

HEPATICAE

Bazzania approximata Ondaedt - End.; M., Sil. (Poes 1995). *P. Ceratolejeunea jungeri* Steph. - Masc.; M., Sil. (Poes 1995). *Lejeunea caespitosa* Lindenb. - End.; M., Sil. (Poes 1995). *L. tuberculosa* Steph. - End.; Sil. (Poes 1995). *Plagiochila aff. fusifera* Teyl. - Sil. (Poes 1995).

MUSCI (all new data determined by C. Townsend) *Acanthorrhynchium decolor* (Besch.) Fleisch. - Afr.; M., Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. 1). *Acrobryopsis crispicuspis* (Besch.) Fleisch. - Afr.; Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. 10). *Aerobryidium subpiligerum* (Hampe) Card. - Afr.; M., Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. B17). *Calymperes hispidum* Ren. & Card. - Madagascar; M., Sil. (Orban 1995). *P. C. taitense* (Sull.) Mitt. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Orban 1995). *Cyclodictyon vallis-gratiene* (Hampe) Broth. - M., Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. B12). *Distichophyllum mascarenicum* Besch. - Afr.; M., Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. 21). *Fissidens* sp. ?; Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 - no number). *Floribundaria floribunda* (D&M) Fleisch. - Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. B6). *Leucomium aneurodictyon* (C.M.) Jaeg. - Afr.; M., Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. B16). *Leucophanes angustifolium* Retz. & Card. - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Orban 1995, new data; OUSE 1990 no. 18). *Porotrichum elongatum* (Welw. & Duby) Gepp - Afr.; M., Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. B18). *Racopilum* sp. - Sil. (new data; OUSE 1990 no. 9).

PTERIDOPHYTA

Family ADIANTACEAE *Acrostichum speciosum* Willd. - W Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *A. aureum*; Kramer 1992), P. & Bird. *Afropteris burklayi* Hooker - End.; M., Sil. (Fleishmann 1995) & P. *Antrophyum callifolium* Blume - Asia; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Pellaea doniana* Hook. - Afr., M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Pteris 'quadriaurita'* - M., Sil. (Kramer 1992) & P. *P. tripartita* Sw. - Palaeotrop.; Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Vitaria ensiformis* Sw. - Masc.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *V. scolopendrina* (Bory) Thwaites - Afr., Asia; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912; Kramer 1992; Fleishmann 1995).

Family ASPLENIACEAE *Asplenium complanatum* C. Chr. - End.; Sil. (Christensen 1912). *A. nidus* L. - Pan-tropics; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912; Friedmann 1986a; OUSE 1990; Kramer 1992; Fleishmann 1995; Mayot 1996b), P. *A. pellucidum* Lam. - Cosmopol.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *A. candidum*; Kramer 1992; Fleishmann 1995). *A. 'protensum'* - (OUSE 1990). *A. 'punctatum'* - (Fleishmann 1995). *A. 'tenerum'* - (OUSE 1990). *A. 'unilaterale'* - (OUSE 1990). *Bolbitis bipinnatifida* (Mett. ex Kuhn) Ching - Masc.; M., Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *Leptochilus bipinnatifidus*; Kramer 1992) & P. *Dryopteris hornei* (Baker) O. Kuntze - End.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *D. mauritiana* (Fee) C. Chr. - W Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *D. wardii* (Baker) O. Kuntze - End.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Elaphoglossum conforme* (Sw.) Schott - Pan-tropics; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *E. hornei* C. Chr. - End.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *E. lancifolium* (Desv.) Morton - Pan-trop.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *E. petiolatum*). *E. latifolium* (Sw.) J. Sm. - Pan-trop.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *E. 'lineatum'* - (Baker 1877). *E. martinicense* (Desv.) T. Moore - Pan-trop.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Polystichum adiantiforme* (Forst.) J. Sm. - Pan-trop., M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Tectaria pleiotoma* (Baker) Kuhn - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *Aspidium pleiotomum*; Fleishmann 1995). *T. 'puberula'* - (OUSE 1990).

Family BLECHNACEAE *Stenochlaena pervillei* (Mett.) Underw. - End.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912).

Family CYATHACEAE *Cyathea sechellarum* Mett. - End.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912; OUSE 1990; Kramer 1992).

Family DAVALLIACEAE *Davallia denticulata* (Burn. f.) Mett. ex Kuhn - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *D. chaerophyllioides*; Kramer 1992). *D. repens* (Linn. f.) Mett. ex Kuhn - Indo-Pacific; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *Humata repens*). *Nephrolepis 'biserrata'* - M., Long, Sil. (Christensen 1912; OUSE 1990; Kramer 1992; Fleishmann 1995), P., A., L.D. & Bird. *Oleandra distenta* Kunze - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *O. articulata*).

Family DENNSTAEDTIACEAE *Lindsaea hirkii* Hooker - End.; M., Sil. (Christensen 1912; Kramer 1992; Fleishmann 1995) & P. *Microlepia speluncae* (L.) Moore - Palaeotrop.; Sil. (Kramer 1992).

- Family GLEICHENIACEAE *Dicranopteris linearis* Burm. - Palaeotrop.; M., Long. Moy., Sil. (Christensen 1912 & OUSE 1990 as *Gleichenia linearis*; Fleischmann 1995) & P.
- Family HYMENOPHYLLACEAE *Hymenophyllum hygroetricum* Desv. - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *H. polyanthos* Sw. - Pantróp., M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912). *Trichomanes cuspidatum* Willd. - M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *T. erosum*). *T. cupressoides* Desv. - Afr., M., Long. Sil. (Christensen 1912; Kramer 1992; Fleischmann 1995) & P.
- Family MARATTIACEAE *Angiopteris madagascariensis* (de Vriese) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912 & OUSE 1990 as *A. evecta*; Kramer 1992; Fleischmann 1995).
- Family OPHIOGLOSSACEAE *Ophioglossum pendulum* Linn. - Asia; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912).
- Family PARKERIACEAE *Ceratopteris cornuta* (Pal.) Lepr. - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *C. thalictoides*), P. & A.
- Family POLYPODIACEAE *Phymatosorus scolopendria* (Burm. f.) Pic. Ser. - Palaeotrop.; M., Long. Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *Polypodium phymatoses*; Fleischmann 1995), P., Co., A., LD. & Bird. *Polypodium albobrunneum* Baker - End.; M. & Sil. (Christensen 1912).
- Family PSILOTAACEAE *Psilotum complanatum* Swartz - Asia; M., Sil. (OUSE 1990 as *P. sp.*), & P.
- Family SELAGINELLACEAE *Selaginella fissidentoides* - (OUSE 1990, Fleischmann 1995).
- Family THELYPTERIDACEAE *Thelypteris subtruncata* (Bory) Panigrahi - Sil. (Kramer 1992). *T. 'omentosa'* - (Fleishmann 1995). *T. unita* (L.) Morton - Indo-Pacific; M., Long & Sil. (Christensen 1912 as *Dryopteris cucullata*).

ANGIOSPERMAE (distribution records are given in Robertson 1989 only summary records are repeated here)

- Family ANNONACEAE *Cananga odorata* (Lam.) Hook. f. & Thoms. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Fleishmann 1995), P. & Freg.
- Family LAURACEAE *Cassytha filiformis* L. - Indo-Pacific; M. & Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Cinnamomum verum* Presl. in Burch. & Presl. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1986a; Robertson 1989, OUSE 1990 & Fleischmann 1995 as *C. zeylanicum*; Matyot 1996b).
- Family HERNANDIACEAE *Hernandia nymphaefolia* (Presl) Kubitzki - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P., A. & LD.
- Family PIPERACEAE *Piper sp.* - Indigenous; Sil. (Friedmann 1986a & 1994; OUSE 1990).
- Family ULMACEAE *Trema orientalis* (L.) Bl. - Afr.-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *T. guineensis*; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989).
- Family MORACEAE *Trilepisium madagascariense* DC. - Mad.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Bosquea gymandra*; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989). *Ficus bojeri* Baker - Mad., Comoros; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986 & 1994; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Fleischmann 1995). *F. lutea* Vahl - Afr., Mad., Comoros, Aldabra; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932, Robertson 1989, OUSE 1990 & Fleischmann 1995 all as *F. nautarum*). *F. rubra* Vahl - Masc., Aldabra; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989 as *F. avic-avic*; Friedmann, P. & Fel. *F. reflexa* Thunb. - Mad., M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *F. sechellarum*; Robertson 1989). *Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lam. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Fleischmann 1995) & P. *A. altilis* (Parkins.) Fosb. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989).
- Family URTICACEAE *Procris insularis* H. Schröter - End.; M. Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 & Robertson 1989 as *P. latifolia*; Friedmann 1994; Fleischmann 1995; Matyot 1996b) & P. *Laportea aestuans* (L.) Chew - Indo-Pacific; S.I. (Averyanov & Kudravytzeva 1987 as *L. interrupta*) & LD.
- Family CASUARINACEAE *Casuarina equisetifolia* J.R. & G. Forster - SE Asia; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995).
- Family NYCTAGINACEAE *Pisonia grandis* R.Br. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), A., Cou., Coe., Bird & Denis. *P. sechellarum* F. Friedmann - End.; M? & Sil. (Friedmann 1987b & 1994; OUSE 1990; Gerlach 1994c). *Mirabilis jalapa* L. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Bougainvillea sp.* - Planted; widespread (NPTS 1996).

- Family CACTACEAE *Opuntia vulgaris* Mill. - Introduced; (NPTS 1996). *Rhipsalis baccifera* (J. Mill.) Stearn - Pan trop.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *R. cassutha*; OUSF 1990; Friedmann 1994) & Fel.
- Family AMARANTHACEAE *Cyathula prostrata* (L.) Bl. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994) & Freg. *Aerva lanata* (L.) Schult. - Introduced; Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Alternanthera sessilis* (L.) DC. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994), P., A. & Freg.
- Family POLYGONACEAE *Polygonum senegalense* Meisn. - Afr.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994).
- Family DILLENIACEAE *Dillenia ferruginea* (Baillon) Gig - End., M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995), P. & Cur.
- Family DIPTEROCARPACEAE *Vateriaopsis seychellarum* (Dyer) Heim - End. gen., M., Sil. (NPTS 1996; new data: timber used in floors of Grande Case, La Passe) & P.
- Family GUTTIFERAE *Calophyllum inophyllum* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995).
- Family TILIACEAE *Triumfetta rhomboidea* Jacq. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989).
- Family STERCULIACEAE *Heritiera littoralis* Ait. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Matyot 1996b), P., Cur. & Freg. *Theobroma cacao* L. - M., Sil. (Matyot 1996b) & P. *Cola nitida* (Vent.) Schott & Endl. - Introduced; (Robertson 1989; Matyot 1996b)
- Family MALVACEAE *Malvastrum coromandelianum* (L.) Garcke - Introduced; Sil. (Friedmann 1994). *Abutilon indicum* (L.) Sweet - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989), Cou. & Denis. *Sida pusilla* Cav. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Baker 1877 as *S. vescoana*) & Freg. *S. acuta* Burm f. - Introduced; widespread (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989). *S. stipulata* Cav. - Introduced; Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & Bird. *Thespesia populnea* (L.) Soland. ex Correa - Indo-Pacific; widespread (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Gossypium hirsutum* L. - Introduced; (new data: Gerlach & Matyot pers. obs. 1990). *Urena lobata* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994).
- Family LEGUMINOSAE *Barringtonia asiatica* (L.) Kurz - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1994). *B. racemosa* (L.) Spreng - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Matyot 1996b) & P.
- Family NEPENTHACEAE *Nepenthes pervillei* Bl. - End.; M. & S. (Baker 1877; Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; OUSF 1990; Malcomber 1994).
- Family FLACOURTIACEAE *Ludia mauritiana* Gmel. - Masc.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; OUSF 1990; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995; Matyot 1996b), P., Cur. & Fel. *Aphloia theiformis* (Vahl) Benn - Mad.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989 & Fleishmann 1995 as *A. seychellensis*; Friedmann 1994) & P. *Flacourtia jangomas* (our.) Rauschel - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Robertson 1989 as *F. ramonchi*; Friedmann 1994).
- Family TURNERACEAE *Turnera angustifolia* Miller - Introduced; widespread (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989 as *T. ulmifolia*).
- Family PASSIFLORACEAE *Adenia gummifera* (Harv.) Harms - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSF 1990; Friedmann 1994; Matyot 1996b). *Passiflora suberosa* L. - Introduced; widespread (Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995). *P. foetida* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995) & P. *P. edulis* Sims - Introduced; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & P.
- Family CARICACEAE *Carica papaya* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1991).
- Family BEGONIACEAE *Begonia seychellensis* Hemsl. - End., M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; OUSF 1990; Matyot 1996b). *B. ulmifolia* Willd. - Introduced; M., Sil. (OUSF 1990 as *B. humilis*; Friedmann 1994) & P.
- Family CAPPARIDACEAE *Cleome viscosa* L. - Introduced; widespread (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989).
- Family EBENACEAE *Diospyros seychellarum* (Hiern) Kosterm. - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994), P. & Fel.

- Family SAPOTACEAE *Northea hornei* (M.M Hartog) Pierre - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989 as *N. seychellana*; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Matyot 1996b), P. & Cur. *Mimusops sechellarum* (Oliv.) Hemsl. - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), P., Fel. & Mar. *Pouteria obovata* (R.Br.) Baehni - Asia-Aust.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Sideroxylon ferrugineum*; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996) & P.
- Family MYRSINACEAE *Rapanea sechellarum* Mez - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994).
- Family PITTOSPORACEAE *Pittosporum senacla* Putterl - Mad., Masc. - M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989 & Fleishmann 1995 as *P. wrightii*; Friedmann 1994).
- Family BREXICEAE *Brexia madagascariensis* (Lam.) Ker Gawl - Mad.; M., Long, Ro., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), P. & Fel.
- Family CRASSULACEAE *Kalanchoë pinnata* (Lam.) Pers. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1994).
- Family ROSACEAE *Rubus rosifolius* J.E. Smith - Asia; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990 as *R. mauritianus*). *R. fraxinifolius* Poir. - Asia; M. & Sil. (Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1994).
- Family CHRYSOBALANACEAE *Chrysobalanus icaco* L. - Introduced; widespread (OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994).
- Family CAESALPINIACEAE *Intsia bijuga* (Colebr.) O.Kuntze - Indian Ocean; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1994).
- Family MIMOSACEAE *Acacia pennata* (L.) Willd. - Asia, Sil. (Friedmann 1986a & 1994; OUSE 1990; Matyot 1996b). *Adenanthera pavonina* L. - Asia; widespread - Sil. (Swabey 1970; Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b). *Mimosa pudica* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991). *Albizia lebbeck* (L.) Benth. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995). *Paraserianthes falcataria* (L.) Niels. - Introduced; widespread (OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b). *Leucaena leucocephala* (Lam.) de Wit - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989).
- Family PAPILIONACEAE *Sophora tomentosa* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1992). *Pterocarpus indicus* Willd. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991). *Abrus precatorius* L. - Afr.-Asia; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989). *Derris trifoliata* Lour. - Indian Ocean; widespread (Summerhayes 1932 as *D. uliginosa*; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989). *Indigofera suffruticosa* Mill. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), N. & Freg. *Desmodium incanum* DC. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989 as *D. canum*). *Erythrina variegata* L. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1996) & P. *Mucuna gigantea* (Willd.) DC. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Matyot 1996b) & Fel. *Canavalia cathartica* Thouars - Indo-Pacific; widespread (Friedmann 1994). *Teramnus labialis* (L.) Spreng. - Pantrop., M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & I.D. *Clitoria ternatea* L. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1994). *Vigna marina* (Burm.) Merr. - Pantrop.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Rhynchosia viscosa* (Roth) DC. - Introduced; Sil. (Friedmann 1994). *Phaesolus lunatus* L. - Introduced; Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989). *Crotalaria pallida* Ait. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & Freg. *C. retusa* L. - Introduced; M., Long, Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989) & Freg.
- Family MYRTACEAE *Syzygium wrightii* (Baker) A.J. Scott - End., M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995), P., Cur. & Fel. *S. jambos* (L.) Alston - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995) & P. *S. aromaticum* (L.) Merr. & Perry - Introduced; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann) & P. *Psidium cattleianum* Sabine - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995 as *P. littorale*; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996). *P. guajava* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994), N., P. & Car.
- Family ONAGRACEAE *Ludwigia octovalvis* (Jacquin) Raven - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Jussiaea suffruticosa*; Friedmann 1994). *L. erecta* (L.) Hara - Afr.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *L. jussiaeoides*; Robertson 1989).

- Family MELASTOMATACTAE: *Memezyton eteagni* Bl. - End.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleischmann 1995). *Melastoma malabathricum* L. - Asia, M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Clidemia hirta* (L.) D. Don - Introduced; Sil. (Averyanov & Kudriavtzeva 1987; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Getlach 1994b; Fleischmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b).
- Family COMBRETACEAE *Lumnitzera racemosa* Willd. - Indian Ocean; widespread (Friedmann 1994). *Terminalia catappa* L. - Asia; widespread (Friedmann 1994; Matyot 1996b).
- Family RHIZOPHORACEAE *Rhizophora mucronata* Lam. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1990; Friedmann 1994) & P. *Ceriops tagal* (Perrotet) C.B. Robins. - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & P. *Bruguiera gymnorhiza* (L.) Lam. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & P.
- Family LORANTHACEAE *Bakerella clavata* (Desrouss.) S. Balle - Mad., Masc.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Loranthus sechellensis*; Friedmann 1994), P. & Cur.
- Family ICACINACEAE: *Grisollea thomassetii* Hemsl. - End., M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995; Matyot 1996b).
- Family EUPHORBIACEAE *Phyllanthus pervilleanus* (Baillon) Muell. Arg. - Mad.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. schimperianus*; Friedmann 1994). *P. anarus* Schumacher & Thonn. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. ururi*; Robertson 1989). *P. tenellus* Roxb. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932) & A. *Wielandia elegans* Baillon - Mad.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995) & P. *Drypetes riseleyi* Airy Shaw - End., M., Sil. (Friedmann 1986 & 1994; Robertson 1989) & P. *Jatropha curcas* L. - Introduced; widespread (Friedmann 1994). *Euphorbia pyrifolia* Lam. - Mad., Masc.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Fleischmann 1995). *E. hirta* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *E. cyathophora* Murr. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *E. heterophylla*). *Hevea brasiliensis* (Willd.) Muell. Arg. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995; Matyot 1996b), P. & Freg. *Manihot glazouii* Muell. Arg. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Friedmann 1994).
- Family RHAMNACEAE *Colubrina asiatica* (L.) Brougn. - Indian Ocean; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989).
- Family ERYTHROXYLACEAE *Erythroxylum sechellarum* O.E. Schulix - End.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994).
- Family SAPINDACEAE *Allophylus pervillei* Blume - Afr., M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Fleischmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996), P., Fel. & LD. *A. sechellensis* Summerh. - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986 & 1994; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996) & P. *Cardiospermum hallicacabum* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989), N., Freg. & Bird. *Dodonaea viscosa* Jacq. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989).
- Family ANACARDIACEAE *Anacardium occidentale* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Fleischmann 1995). *Mangifera indica* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleischmann 1995). *Spondias cytherea* Sonn. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989).
- Family SIMARUBACEAE *Soulamea terminalloides* Baker - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994).
- Family MELIACEAE *Xylocarpus moluccensis* (Lam.) Roem. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1994), N. & P. *Sandoricum koetjape* (Burn.f.) Merrill - Introduced; M., Sil. (Fleischmann 1995 as *S. indicum*), N. & P. *Swietenia macrophylla* King - M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P. & Freg. *Melia dubia* Cav. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994) & P.
- Family RUTACEAE *Murraya paniculata* (L.) Jack - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), P. & LD. *Citrus spp.* - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Fleischmann 1995).
- Family OXALIDACEAE *Oxalis corniculata* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P. & Freg. *Averrhoa bilimbi* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932).
- Family BALSAMINACEAE *Impatiens gordonii* Hornem ex Baker - End., M. & Sil. (Baker 1877; Matyot 1996b).
- Family ARIALACEAE *Schefflera procumbens* (Hemsl.) F. Friedmann - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1987a & 1994; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990). *Gastonia*

- sechellarum* (Baker) Harms - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1987a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996), P., Cur. & Fel. *G. crassa* (Hemsl.) F. Friedmann - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994) & P.
- Family UMBELLIFERAE *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urb. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989)
- Family LOGANIACEAE *Strychnos spinosa* Lam. - Afr.; M., SA., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), P. & Freg.
- Family APOCYNACEAE *Carissa edulis* (Forssk.) Vahl - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *C. sechellensis*; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996). *Cerbera manghas* L. - Indo-Pacific; M. Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994), P., & Cur. *Ochrosia oppositifolia* (Lam.) K. Schum. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *O. parvifolia*; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Tabernaemontana coffeoides* Boj. ex A. DC. - Mad.; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Alstonia macrophylla* Wall. ex G. Don - Introduced; M., SA., Sil. (Fleischmann 1995), P. & Freg. *Catharanthus roseus* (L.) G. Don - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (*new data*; Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991).
- Family ASCLEPIADACEAE *Tylophora coriacea* Murais - Masc.; Sil. (OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996). *Sarcostemma viminale* (L.) Aiton f. - Afr.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleischmann 1995). *Asclepias curassavica* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994) & L.D. *Gomphocarpus physocarpus* E. Mey. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Friedmann 1994). *G. fruticosus* (L.) Aiton f. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994) & Freg.
- Family SOLANACEAE *Solanum americanum* Mill. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *S. nodiflorum*; Robertson 1989 as *S. nigrum*). *Physalis angulata* L. - Introduced; Long, Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994), L.D., & Freg. *Datura metel* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1994).
- Family CONVULVULACEAE *Ipomoea pes-caprae* (L.) R. Br. - Pantrop.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989). *I. macrantha* Roem. & Schult. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989). *I. venosa* (Desr.) Roem. & Schult. - Masc.?; M., Anon., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994, Matyot 1996b), Cou., Coue. & A. *I. mauritiana* Jacq. - Pantrop.; M., SA., Sil. (Friedmann 1994) & N. *I. aquatica* Forssk. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), N., Cur. & A. *Merremia peltata* (L.) Merr. - Indo-Pacific; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Fleischmann 1995).
- Family BORAGINACEAE *Tournefortia puberula* Baker - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 & Robertson 1989 as *T. sarmentosa*; Friedmann 1994). *T. argentea* L.f. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989). *Heliotropium indicum* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994).
- Family VERBENACEAE *Clerodendrum speciosissimum* Merr. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (*new data*; Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991). *Prenna serratifolia* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. corymbosa*; Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995). *Phyla nodiflora* (L.) Greene - Pantrop.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Stachytarpheta jamaicensis* (L.) Vahl - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Fleischmann 1995). *S. urticifolia* (Saitsh.) Sims - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Lantana camara* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Fleischmann 1995). *Vitex trifolia* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932).
- Family AVICENNIACEAE *Avicennia marina* (Forssk.) Vierh. - Indian Ocean; widespread - Sil. (*new data*; Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1996).
- Family LABIATAE *Achyropernum sechellarum* Baker - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b). *Plectranthus amboinicus* (Lour.) Spreng - Asia; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Coleus subfrutescens*; Friedmann 1994), N., P., A. & Cou. *Leucas lavandulifolia* J.E. Sm. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), N. & Freg. *Pogostemon heyneanus* Benth. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994). *Ocimum gratissimum* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989) & N.
- Family PLANTAGINACEAE *Plantago major* L. - Introduced; Sil. (Robertson 1989)
- Family OLEACEAE *Jasminum fluminense* Vellozo - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Friedmann 1986a & 1994)

- Family SCROPHULARIACEAE *Scoparia dulcis* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994), P. & Freg. *Striga usitica* (L.) O. Kuntze - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989).
- Family ACANTHACEAE *Asystasia* sp. B. - ?; widespread - Sil. (Fleishmann 1995 as *A. gangetica*). *Pseuderanthemum tunicatum* (Afz.) Milne Redl. - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. malabahrutum*; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; OUSE 1990; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b). *Justicia genundarua* Burm.f. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991), P., Cur. & LD. *Justicia gardineri* Tur. - Ind.; Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Thunbergia alata* Boj. ex Sims - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *T. erecta*; Friedmann 1994).
- Family BIGNONIACEAE *Colea seychellarum* Seem. - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *C. pedunculata*; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995). *Tabeuia pallida* (Lindl.) Niers - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1986a; Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995).
- Family CAMPANULACEAE *Hippobroma longiflora* (L.) G. Don - Introduced; M., Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1994), P. & Cur.
- Family GOODENACEAE *Scaevola sericea* Vahl - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991).
- Family RUBIACEAE *Psathura sechellarum* Baker - End.; M. & Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Psychotria pervillei* Baker - Ald.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1990; Fleishmann 1995) & P. *P. silhouettes* F. Friedmann - End.; Sil. (Friedmann 1990 & 1994; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b). *Amaracarpus pubescens* Bl. - Asia; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1986a & 1994; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996). *Morinda citrifolia* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995; Matyot 1996b). *Craterispermum microdon* Baker - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994) & P. *Pentodon pentandrus* (Schumacher & Thonn.) Vatke - Afr.; widespread - Sil. (Baker 1877 & Robertson 1989 as *Oldenlandia hornei*). *Glionnetia sericea* (Baker) Tirv.; End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994). *Rothamnia annae* (Wright) Keay - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), P., A. & Fel. *Ixora pudica* Baker - End.; M. & Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Turrena sechellensis* (Baker) Summerh. - Ald., M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995; Carlstrom *et al.* 1996; Matyot 1996b), P., Cur. & Fel. *Paragneipa wrightii* (Baker) F. Friedmann - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 & Robertson 1989; as *Randia lanceifolia*; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995), P., Cur. & Fel. *Vangueria madagascariensis* J.F. Gmel. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989) & N. *Canthium bibracteatum* (Baker) Hiem - Afr.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995). *C. carinatum* (Bak.) Summerh. - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994) & P. *C. sechellense* Summerh. - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994). *Coffea* sp. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1991). *Guetarda speciosa* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Timonius sechellensis* Summerh. - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995) & P.
- Family COMPOSITAE *Vernonia cinerea* (L.) Less. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach *pers. obs.* 1994). *Elephantopus mollis* H.B.K. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *E. scaber*; Robertson 1989). *Gynura sechellensis* (Baker) Hemsl. - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1994; Fleishmann 1995). *Emilia sonchifolia* (L.) Wright - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), N. & Freg. *Ageratum conyzoides* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932) & Freg. *Tridax procumbens* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Bidens pilosa* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Parthenium hysterophorus* L. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Synedrella nodiflora* (L.) Gaertn. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1994). *Sigesbeckia orientalis* L. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Friedmann 1994). *Pterocypsela indica* (L.) Shih - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Lactuca mauritiana*).

- Family ORCHIDACEAE *Acampe praemosa* (Roxb.) Blatter & MacCann - Ald.; Sil (Friedmann 1986a as *A. rigida*). *Agrostophyllum occidentale* Schltr. - Ind.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932, Robertson 1989). *Angraecum eburneum* Bory - Mad.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *A. brongniartianum*) & *P. A. zeylanicum* Lindl. - Asia; M. & Sil. (Friedmann 1986a as *A. mahense*; Carlstrom et al. 1996). *Bulbophyllum intertextum* Lindl. - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *B. seychellarum*; Robertson 1989). *Cynorkis fastigiata* Thouars - Mad.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Robertson 1989), P. & Cur. *C. seychellarum* Aver. - End.; M., Sil. (Aeryanov & Kudriavtzeva 1987), P. & Fel. *Disperis tripetaloides* (Thouars) Lindl. - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932) & *P. Eulopia pulchra* (Thouars) Lindl. - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1986a) & *P. Graphorkis scripta* (Thouars) Kuntze - Indian Ocean, Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Eulopia* sp.). *Hederorkis seychellensis* Bosser - Ald.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Bulbophyllum scandens*; Friedmann 1986a). *Malaxis seychellarum* (Kraenzl.) Summerh. - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932, Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995). *Oeonitella aphrodite* Schltr. - Masc.; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1986a as *O. polystachys*; Robertson 1989) & *P. Phalus tetragonus* (Thouars) Reichb.f. - Masc.; M. & Sil. (Friedmann 1986a; OUSE 1990). *Platyplepis gooderyoides* A.Rich. - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. occulta*). *P. sechellarum* S.Moore - End.; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Polystachya concreta* (Jacq.) Garay & Sweet - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. mauritiana*; Robertson 1989). *Vanilla phalaenopsis* Reichb.f. - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P. & Fel. *V. planifolia* Andrews - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Fleishmann 1995).
- Family ZINGIBERACEAE *Elettaria cardamomum* Maton - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Fleishmann 1995).
- Family MUSACEAE *Musa* sp. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Matyot 1996b).
- Family HYPOXIDACEAE *Curculigo sechellensis* Boj. - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P. & Freg. *Hypoxidia rhizophylla* (Baker) F.Friedmann - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; Friedmann 1988; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995), P., Cur. & LD.
- Family AGAVACEAE *Agave sisalana* (Perr. ex Engelm.) Drumm. & Prain - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1994).
- Family BROMELIACEAE *Ananas comosus* (L.) Merr. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Fleishmann 1995).
- Family TACCACEAE *Tacca leontopetaloides* (L.) O.Kuntze - Introduced; M., SA., Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1994) & P.
- Family LILIACEAE *Dracaena reflexa* La. - Mad.; widespread - Sil. (Friedmann 1986a, OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995; Matyot 1996b).
- Family COMMELINACEAE *Commelina bengalensis* L. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *C. diffusa* Burb.f. - Introduced; Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *C. nudiflora*) & N.
- Family FLAGELLARIACEAE *Flagellaria indica* L. - Asia; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995), P., Cur. & Fel.
- Family PALMAE *Cocos nucifera* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread (Robertson 1989; Fleishmann 1995; Matyot 1996b). *Deckeria nobilis* Wendl. - Ind.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995). *Lodoicea maldivica* (Gmel.) Pers. - End. gen.; Sil. (OUSE 1990), P., Cur., R. & SP. *Nephrosperma vanhouetteana* (Wendl. ex van-Houtt.) Balf. - End. gen.; M., SA., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995), P. & Cur. *Phoenixophorium horsiganum* (K.Koch) Stuntz - End. gen.; widespread - Sil. (Scott 1913 as *Stevensonia granifolia*; Summerhayes 1932, OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995, Matyot 1996b). *Roscheria melanochaetes* (Wendl.) Wendl. ex Balf. - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995, Matyot 1996b) & *P. Verschaffeltia splendida* Wendl. - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Friedmann 1986a; Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995) & P.
- Family PANDANACEAE *Pandanus balfourii* Mart. - Ind.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932) *P. hornii* Balf.f. - End.; M., Sil. (Baker 1877; OUSE 1990; Fleishmann 1995), P. & Cur. *P. multispicatus* Balf.f. - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P., Cur. & Freg. *P. sechellarum* Balf.f. - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; OUSE 1990; fleishmann 1995), P. & LD.

- Family TYPHACEAE *Typha javanica* Schnitzl. ex Zoll. - Asia; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932)
- Family ARACEAE *Culadium* sp. - Introduced; M., Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs 1994) & Freg *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs 1994) *Philodendron* sp. - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs 1994). *Protarum sechellarum* - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; OUSE 1990, Fleischmann 1995, Carlstrom et al. 1996) & P
- Family TRIURIDACEAE *Seychellaria thomassetii* Hemsley - End.; M., Sil. (OUSE 1990, Carlstrom et al. 1996) & P.
- Family CYPERACEAE *Cyperus articularis* L. - Pantrap.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), N., P. & LD. *Eleocharis dulcis* (Burm.f.) Trin. - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *E. plantaginoides*; Robertson 1989) & Cur. *Fimbristylis complanata* (Retz.) Link - Introduced?; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932, Robertson 1989). *Fimbristylis cymosa* R.Br. - Pantrap.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *F. spathacea*). *F. dichotoma* (L.) Vahl - Introduced?; M., Long, Sil. (Robertson 1989), P & Freg. *Kyllinga colorata* (L.) Drace - Introduced?; M. & Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *K. brevifolia*; Robertson 1989) *K. polyphylla* Willd. ex Kunth - Indian Ocean; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989). *K. tenuifolia* Steud. - Introduced?; M., Sil. (Averyanov & Kudriavtzeva 1987) & Fel. *Lophoscoenus hornei* (C.B.Cl.) Stapf - End.; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995), P. & Cur. *Mapania floribundum* - End.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *Thoracostachyum angustifolium*) & P. *Marsicus dubius* (Rottb.) Fischer - Pantrap.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *M. dregeanus*). *M. panicus* (Rottb.) Vahl - Asia, Masc., M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), P., Fel & LD. *M. pennatus* (Lam.) Domin. - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), P., Co., Cur. *Pycurus polystachyus* (Rottb.) P.Beauv. - Indian Ocean, widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *P. odoratus*). *Scleria sieberi* Nees ex Kunth - Mad.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *S. angusta*) & P.
- Family GRAMINAE *Axonopus compressus* (L.) P.Beauv. - Introduced?; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), N. & Freg. *Bracharia umbellata* (Trin.) W.D.Claydon - Mad.; widespread - Sil. (Fleishmann 1995). *Coix lachryma-jobi* L. - Introduced; M., Sil. (new data: Gerlach, pers. obs. 1990) & Freg. *Cymbopogon pruinosis* (Nees ex Steud.) Chiov. - Introduced?; Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Cyrtococcum oxyphyllum* Stapf - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932) & P. *Dactyloctenium ctenoides* (Steud.) Bosser - Pantrap.; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *D. aegyptium*). *Dichanthium aristatum* (Poir.) Hubb. - Introduced?; Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Digitaria horizontalis* Willd. - Introduced?; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *D. radicata* (Presl) Miq. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *D. pruriens*). *Echinochloa colonum* (L.) Link - Introduced?; M., SA., Sil. (Robertson 1989) & N. *Elusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. - Introduced?; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Eragrostis tenella* (L.) P>Beauv. - Introduced?; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Garnotia sechellensis* Hubb. & Summerh. - End. M. & Sil. (Friedmann 1986a; Robertson 1989). *Hyperrhenia rufa* (Nees) Stapf - Introduced?; M., Sil. (Robertson 1989), P. & Cur. *Optismenus compositus* (L.) P.Beauv. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Panicum brevifolium* L. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Robertson 1989; Fleischmann 1995). *P. maximum* L. - Introduced?; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932; Fleischmann 1995). *Paspalidium geminatum* (Forsk.) Stapf - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), N. & Freg. *P. scrobiculatum* L. - Palaeotrop.; M., Long, Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), N. & Freg. *Pennisetum polystachyus* (L.) Schult. - Introduced?; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932). *Setaria barbata* (Lam.) Kunth - Introduced?; M., SA., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932), N. & Freg. *Sorghum arundinaceum* (Desv.) Stapf - Introduced; M., Sil. (Summerhayes 1932 as *S. verticilliflorum*) & P. *Sporobolus diander* (Retz.) P.Beauv. - Introduced?; M & Sil. (Robertson 1989). *Stenotaphrum dimidiatum* (L.) Brongn. - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Summerhayes 1932).

ANIMALIA

NEMERTEA

ENOPLA

Family GÉONEMERTIDAE *Geonemertes pelsaensis* Semper, 1863 - Indo-Pacific; M., Long & Sil. (OUSE 1990 all as *G. arhscola*).

ANNELIDA

OLIGOCHAETA

Family MEGASCOLECIDAE *Amyntas rodericensis* (Grube) - Indian Ocean; Sil. (Sims 1981)

HIRUDINEA

Family IDIOBDELLIDAE *Idiobdella seychellensis* Harding, 1913 - End. gen.; Sil. (Harding 1913; Richardson 1978; OUSE 1990). *I. daubani* Richardson, 1978 - End.; Sil. (Richardson 1978; OUSE 1990).

MOLLUSCA

Family STREPTAXIDAE *Edentulina dussumieri* (Dufa, 1840) End.; Sil. (Nevill 1868; Martens 1898; Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *E. moreleti* (Adams, 1868) - End.; M., Sil. (Adams 1868; Sykes 1909; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *Guilla gardineri* (Sykes, 1909) - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *G. silhouettanus* Verdcourt, 1996 - End.; Sil. (Verdcourt 1996; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *Streptaxis souleyetanus* (Petit, 1834) - End.; M., Sil. (Nevill 1868; Martens 1898; Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *P.*, Cur. & LD. *Stereosele nevillei* (Adams, 1868) - End.; M., Sil. (Martens 1898; Sykes 1909; Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.) & *P.* *Streptosele acicula* Morelet - W. Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *Imperturbatia* n. sp. - End. gen.; Sil. (Martens 1898; Sykes 1909 & OUSE 1990 as *I. constans*; Barnacle 1971 as *I. le-vieuxi*; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *I. perlegans* Martens, 1898 - End.; M. & Sil. (OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *Augustula braueri* (Martens, 1898) - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Martens 1898; Sykes 1909; Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *Acantheneia erinaceus* Martens, 1898 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Martens 1898; Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & van Bruggen in prep.). *Priondiscus serratus* (Adams 1868) - End. gen.; Sil. (Adams 1868; Sykes 1909 as *P. martensi*; OUSE 1990; Gerlach 1996c). *Priondiscus spinatus* Gerlach, 1996 - End.; Sil. (Gerlach 1996b; OUSE 1990 as *P.* sp.)

Family ACHATINIDAE *Achatina fulica* Bowditch - Introduced; most islands; Sil. (Nevill 1869; Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990)

Family CAECILIIDAE *Caeciloides mauritiana* (Adams, 1868) - Masc.; M & Sil. (OUSE 1990)

Family SUBULINIDAE *Subulina octona* Bruguière - Pantrop.; most islands - Sil. (Sykes 1909; Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990). *Allopeas javanicum* (Reeve) - Pantrop.; most islands - Sil. (Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990). *A. pumilum* (Pfeiffer) - Pantrop.; most islands - Sil. (Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990). *A. gracile* (Hutton) - Pantrop.; most islands - Sil. (Nevill 1869 as *Subulina mauritiana*; Gerlach 1987 OUSE 1990)

Family HELICIDAE *Bradybaena similaris* (Fertussac) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Sykes 1909; Gerlach 1987). *P.* & LD.

Family ENIDAE *Pachnodus silhouettanus* Van Mol & Benoit, 1980 - End. gen.; Sil. (Nevill 1868 as *Buliminus fulvicans*; Sykes 1909 as *P. ornatus*; Van Mol & Benoit 1980). *P. axoniensis* Gerlach, 1995 - End.; Sil. (OUSE 1990 as *P.* sp.; Gerlach 1994a). *P. lionneti* Van Mol &

- Benoit 1980 - End., Sil. (Nevill 1868 as *Bulininus niger*; Van Mol & Benoit 1980; OUSE 1990).
- Family ZONITIDAE '*Kaliella*' *subturrilita* (Nevill, 1871) - End. gen., M., Sil. (Nevill 1869 as *Helix* n.sp?; Gerlach in prep)
- Family HELICARIONIDAE *Pilula mahesiana* Martens, 1898 - End., M. & Sil. (Martens & Weigmann 1898; OUSE 1990)
- Family ACAVIDAE *Styladonta undulata* (Chemnitz, 1795) - End. gen.; M., St. Anne, Sil. (Nevill 1869; Martens & Weigmann 1898; Sykes 1909; Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990), P., Cur., Fel. & LD
- Family EUCONULIDAE *Liardetia sculpta* (Möllendorf) - Introduced., M., Sil. (OUSE 1990) & P.
- Family PUNCTIDAE *Punctum* n. sp. End., M., Sil. (OUSE 1990 as 'Endoclonitid')
- Family PUPILLIDAE *Gastrocopta tripunctata* Morelet - Mad.; M., Anon., (Martens & Weigmann 1898 as *Pupa microscopica*, OUSE 1990), P., A. & Freg.
- Family SUCCINEIDAE *Quickia concisa* (Morelet) - Mad.; M., Sil. (Nevill 1869 as *Succinea ?striata*; Gerlach 1987; OUSE 1990), P., Fel.
- Family VAGINULIDAE *Vaginula seychellensis* Fischer, 1871 - End.; M., Sil. (Simroth 1913, OUSE 1990) & P. *V. voelzkowi* Simroth 1913 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Simroth 1913 as *V. braueri* & *V. parva*; OUSE 1990). *Semperula maculata* Templeton, 1888 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Simroth 1913 as *V. plana*).
- Family CYCLOPHORIDAE *Cyathopoma blanfordi* Adams, 1868 - End.; M., Sil. (Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990), P. & LD.
- Family POMATISIDAE *Trapidophora pulchra* (Gray, 1834) - End.; M., Sil. (Nevill 1869; Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990), P., LD & Freg.
- Family HELICIDAE *Helicina theobaldiana* Nevill, 1871. - End; M., Anon., Sil. (Nevill 1869; OUSE 1990), P. & LD.
- Family NERITIDAE *Neritina gagates* Lamarck, 1822 - Mnd.; M. & Sil. (*new data*: 1994, NPTS M1997.22). *Neritilla consmilis* (Martens, 1879) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (*new data*: 1994, NPTS M1997.23). *Septaria borbonica* (Bory St. Vincent, 1803) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Gerlach & Canning 1996).
- Family ASSIMINEIDAE *Syncera nitida* (Pease, 1864) - Indo-Pacific; M. & Sil. (Gerlach 1994a).
- Family THIRIDAE *Paludomus ajanensis* Morelet, 1860 - End.; M. & Sil. (Nevill 1869; Sykes 1909 as *P. baccula*; Starmuhner 1983; OUSE 1990; Brown & Gerlach 1991) *Melanoides tuberculatus* (Mullet, 1774) - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Sykes 1909; OUSE 1990; Gerlach 1994a), P. & LD.
- Family POTAMIDIDAE *Terebralia palustris* (Linnaeus, 1767) - Indo-Pacific, M. & Sil. (OUSE 1990; Gerlach 1994a).

CRUSTACEA

DECAPODA

- Family COENOBITIDAE *Coenobita brevimanus* Dana, 1852 - Indo-Pacific; Sil. (Borradaile 1907 as *C. clypeatus*; *new data*: 1994, Gerlach, NPTS D1997.1) & A.
- Family GECARCINIDAE *Cardisoma carnifex* (Herbst, 1784) - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1994b, *new data*: 1994, Gerlach, NPTS D1997.2) & P. *Ocyropode ceratophthalma* (Pallas) - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (*new data*: Gerlach pers. obs. 1990), P., A., Co. & Coc. *Uca annulipes* (Milne Edwards) - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1994b) & P.
- Family GRAPSIDAE *Geograpsus crinipes* (Dana, 1851) - Indian Ocean; Sil. (Borradaile 1907) *Grapsus tenuicrustatus* (Herbst, 1783) - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (*new data*: 1994, Gerlach NPTS D1997.3) & A. *Sesarma intermedium* (De Haan) - Indian Ocean; Sil. (Borradaile 1907). *Sesarma impressum* Milne Edwards - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Borradaile 1907 as *S. longipes*; Gerlach 1994b) & P.

Family CARIDINIDAE *Curidina brevirostris* Stimpson, 1860 - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Bouvier 1914) & P.

Family PALAEMONIDAE *Macrobranchium lar* (Fabricius) - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Borradaile 1907) & P.

ISOPODA

Family ARMADILLIDAE *Cubaris murina* Brandt, 1833 - Masc.; M., Sil. (Budde-Lund 1913), P., Cur. & Mar. *Reductioniscus costulatus* Kesselyak, 1930 - End.; M., Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983, OUSE 1990), P. & Cur. *Sphaerillo maculosus* Budde-Lund, 1904 - End.; M. & Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983). *Venezillo parvus* (Budde-Lund 1885) - Masc., Ascension; M., Sil. (Budde-Lund 1913; Ferrara & Taiti 1983) & P.

Family IRMAOSIDAE *Irmaos sechellarum* Ferrara & Taiti, 1983 - End.; M. & Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983). *Irmaos lobatus* Ferrara & Taiti, 1983 - End.; M. & Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983, OUSE 1990 as *Aphiloscia annulicornis*).

Family PHILOSCIIDAE *Bilawrenzia occidentalis* Ferrara & Taiti, 1983 - End.; Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983), P. & Cur. *Mahchia bicornis* Budde-Lund, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Budde-Lund 1913). *Pseudophiloscia lateralis* Budde-Lund, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Budde-Lund 1913), P. & Mar. *Setaphora pallidemaculata* Budde-Lund, 1913; End.; M., Sil. (Budde-Lund 1913) & P. *Seychelloscia benoitii* Ferrara & Taiti - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983). *S. mucronata* Ferrara & Taiti, 1983 - End.; Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983). *S. vanmolti* Ferrara & Taiti, 1983 - End.; M. & Sil. (Ferrara & Taiti 1983).

ARACHNIDA

ARANEAE

Suborder MYGALOMORPHIA

Family BARYCHELIDAE Simon, 1889 *Sason seychellanum* Simon, 1898 - End.; M., Sil. (Hirst 1911); *new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.283&AA0.313).

Family THERAPHOSIDAE *Chaetopelma gardineri* Hirst, 1911 - End.; M., Sil. (Hirst 1911), P. & Fél.

Suborder ARANEOMORPHA

Family SCYTODIDAE Blackwall, 1864 '*Scytodes*' *pholcoides* Simon, 1898 - End.; M. & Sil. (*new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.057&AA0.323).

Family TELEMIDAE Fage, 1913 *Seychellia wilhoi* Saaristo, 1978 - End. genus; M., Sil. (Brignoli 1980) & LD.

Family OCHYROCERATIDAE Fage, 1912 *N. gen., n. sp.* - *Material*: Sil., 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA 0.074)

Family PHOLCIDAE C. L. Koch, 1851 *N. gen., n. sp.* - *Material*: Sil. 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA0.280-282). '*Holocnemus*' *cuticulus* Simon, 1898 - End.; M. & Sil. (*new data*: 2-8.7.1972, Benoit & van Mol, MRAC 143.373). *Smeringopus pallidus* (Blackwall, 1858) - Pantrop.; M., Long, S. (*new data*: 2-8.7.1972, Benoit & van Mol MRAC 143.373), P.

Family TETRABLEMMIDAE O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873 *Mariblemma pandani* (Brignoli, 1978) - Monotypic end. genus; Sil. (Brignoli 1978). *Tetrablemma benoitii* (Brignoli, 1978) - End.; Sil. (*new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.075) & LD.

- Family OONOPIDAE Simon, 1890 *Lionnetta savyi* (Benoit, 1979), n. comb. - Recorded from M. (type locality) & Sil. (Benoit 1979a). *L. seychellensis* Benoit, 1979 - End.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1979a; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.058), P. & Cur. *Lionnetta silhouettei* Benoit, 1979 - Only the holotype of this species has been collected from Sil. (Benoit 1979a) *Lionnetta* n. sp. 1. - Material: Sil., 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA0.060). *Lionnetta* n. sp. 2. - Material: Sil., 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA0.302). *Lionnetta* n. sp. 3. - Material: Sil., 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA0.061). *Lionnetta* n. sp. 4. - Material: Sil., 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA0.059). *Silhouetella cuiensei* Benoit, 1979 - End genus; Sil. (Benoit 1979a). Cur. & LD. *Stenoops opisthornatus* Benoit, 1979 - End.; Sil. (Benoit 1979a), P. & LD. *Gamasomorpha mornensis* Benoit, 1979 - End.; M. & Sil. (Benoit 1979a; new data: 1990, MZT AA0.064&0.065 & 20.12.1993, MZT AA0.309, all Gerlach). *'G.' sechellensis* Benoit, 1979 - End.; M., Sil. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.067), P. & LD. *'G.' silhouettei* Benoit, 1979 - End.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1979a; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.073) & P.
- Family PALPIMANIDAE Thorell, 1870 *Hybosida dauban* Platnik, 1979 - End gen.; Sil. (Platnik 1979; new data: 1993, Gerlach, MZT AA0.293-0.294).
- Family ULOBORIDAE Thorell, 1869 *Zosis geniculatus* (Oliver, 1789) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978), P. & Cur. *Uloborus plumipes* Lucas, 1846 - Afr.; M., Sil., (Benoit 1978; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.319-321), P., Cur
- Family THERIDIIDAE Sundevall, 1833 *Argyrodes rostratus* Blackwall, 1877 - End.; M., Sil. (Roberts 1978, new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.187), Cur., LD. *A. fissifrontella* Saaristo, 1978 - End.; M. & Sil. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.197). *A. cognatus* (Blackwall, 1877 - End.; M., Sil. (Roberts 1978; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.194-196) & P. *A. recurvatus* Saaristo, 1978 - End.; M. & Sil. (Roberts 1978; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.198-199) *Moneta coerconvus* (Roberts, 1978) n. comb. - End.; M. & Sil. (Simon 1898). *Coleosoma floridana* Banks, 1900 - Cos.; M., Sil. (Roberts 1978), P. & LD. *'Theridion' libudum* Roberts, 1978 - End.; M., Sil. (Roberts 1978; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.217-220). *'T.' braueri* Simon, 1898 - End.; M. & Sil. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.221). N. gen., n. sp. - Material: Sil., 1990, Gerlach (MZT AA0.223).
- Family THERIDIOSOMATIDAE *Zoma zoma* Saaristo, 1996 - Only the holotype of this monotypic genus has been recorded from Sil. (Saaristo 1996a). *Andasta silte* Saaristo, 1996 - Only the holotype from Sil. (Saaristo 1996a).
- Family SYMPHYTOGNATHIDAE Hickman, 1931 *Patu silho* Saaristo, 1996 - Only the holotype and paratype from Sil. (Saaristo 1996b) *Anapistuta seychellensis* Saaristo, 1996 - Only the holotype from Sil. (Saaristo 1996b).
- Family MYSMENIDAE: *Microdopoena elsae* Saaristo, 1979 - End.; M., Sil. (Roberts 1978; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.273) & P.
- Family LINYPHIIDAE Blackwall, 1859 *Nesioneta benoitii* (van Helsdingen, 1978) - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (van Helsdingen 1978), P., Aride, Cos., Petit Soeur & LD.
- Family TETRAGNATHIDAE Menge, 1866 *Nephila inaurata* (Walckenaer, 1841) - W. Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978; Hirst 1911), P., Cur., LD & Frég. *Nephilengys cruentata* (Fabricius, 1775) - Pantrop.; M., Sil., (Benoit 1978, Hirst 1911; Simon 1898; new data: Gerlach, MZT AA0.234-235), P., Cur. & Frég. *'Leucauge' argyrescens* Benoit, 1978 - End.; M., S. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA 0.240) & P. *Mesida thorellii* (Blackwall, 1877), n. comb. - End.; M. Sil. (Benoit 1978; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA 0.236-237) & P. *Tylorida mornensis* (Benoit, 1978), n. com. - End.; M. & Sil. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.238-239) *Tetragnatha foliifera* Simon, 1879 - End.; M. & Sil. (Simon 1893). *T. marginata* (Thorell, 1890) - Pantrop.; M. & Sil. (Hirst 1911 as *T. modesta*). *T. nigricularis* Simon, 1897 - End.; M., Sil. (Hirst 1911), P., Cur. & Fél.
- Family ARANEIDAE *Cyrtophora citricola* (Forskål, 1775) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Hirst 1911; new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.252), P., Cur., LD. *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vison, 1863 - Afr.n species found only on Sil. (Grasshoff 1980; Hirst 1911). *Polys horridus* Locket, 1980 - Comoros. 1 in specimens of *Arachnura scorpionoides* (Grasshoff 1980) - Sil. *Cyclosa kibonotensis* Tullgren, 1910 - Afr.n species recorded from Sil. (Grasshoff 1980). *C. insulana* (Costa, 1834) - Palaeotrop.; M. & Sil. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.253). *Drexella bifida* (Tullgren, 1910) - Afr.n; M. & Sil. (new data: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.268). *Prasconia seriata* (Simon, 1895) - Afr.n; M., Sil. (Grasshoff 1980) & Cur. *Neoscona*

- triangula* (Keyserling, 1864) - M., Sil. (*new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.270) P. & LD. *N. morelii* (Vinson, 1863) - SE Asia-Aust.-Polynesia; M., Sil. (Hirst 1911), Bird. Coertiv. Farquar & St.Pierre
- Family OXYOPIDAE Thorell, 1870 *Oxyopes dumonti* (Vison, 1863) - Afr.n; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978) & P.
- Family CLUBIONIDAE Wagner, 1887 *Clubiona mahensis* Simon, 1893 - End.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978; Hirst 1911) & P. '*C.*' *nigromaculosa* Blackwall, 1877 - End.; M., Anon., Sil. (Saaristo 1995), Aride & Co.a.
- Family ZODARIIDAE Thorell, 1886 *Cryptothela alluandi* Simon, 1893 - End.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978), P., LD & Frég.
- Family SELENOPIDAE Simon, 1897 *Selenops secretus* Hirst, 1911 - End.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978), P. & Frég.
- Family HETEROPODIDAE Thorell, 1874 (Family SPARASSIDAE Simon, 1874) *Rithymna valida* (Blackwall, 1877) - End.; M., Sil., (Benoit 1978) P., LD, Fré. & Bird. *Thomasettia seychellana* Hirst, 1911 - End.; M., Sil. (Benoit 1978) & P. *Rhacocnemis guttata* (Blackwall, 1877) - M., Sil. (Benoit 1978; Hirst 1911 as *R. elegans*), P. & Cur. *Heteropoda vanatoria* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Observed 1990 - J. Gerlach), P. & Bird.
- Family THOMISIDAE Sundevall, 1833 '*Thomisus*' *stenningi* Pocock, 1900 - Mulié, Sil. (Benoit 1978 '*T. citrinellus*?), P. & Cur.
- Family SALTICIDAE Blackwall, 1841 *Goleba pallens* (Blackwall, 1877) - Aldabra and Sil. (Wanless 1980 & 1984) & Denis. *Sadix gibbosa* Wanless, 1984 - End. genus; Sil & LD (Wanless 1984) *Myrmarachne constrictus* (Blackwall, 1877) - End.; Long, Sil. (Wanless 1984; *new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZTAA 0.154), P. & Denis. *Baviola braueri* Simon, 1897 - End. genus; M., Sil. (Wanless 1984) & P. *B. lutesignata* Wanless, 1983 - Long & M. & Sil (*new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.168). *B. spatulata* Wanless 1984 - Found only on Sil. (Wanless 1984). *B. vanmoli* Wanless 1984 - Found on M. & Sil (Wanless 1984). *Hispo alboclypea* Wanless, 1984 - End.; M. & Sil (Wanless 1984; *new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.165-167). *Hasarius rufociliatus* Simon, 1897 - End.; M., Sil. (Wanless 1984; *new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.149), Cur., Fél. *Hyllus acutus* (Blackwall, 1877) - End.; M., Cerf, Sil (Wanless 1984), P., Denis & P., Providence. *Carrhotus bellus* Wanless, 1984 - End.; M., Sil. (Wanless 1984) & P. *Salpesia soricina* Simon, 1901 - End.; locality ? (Wanless 1984), Sil. (*new data*: 1990, Gerlach, MZT AA0.150). *Heliophanus activus* (Blackwall, 1877) - End.; M., Sil. (Wanless 1984), P. & Cur.

OPIIIONES (New data determined by M. Rambla)

- Family PHALANGODIDAE *Ibalonius inscriptus* Loman, 1902 - End.; M., Sil. (Rambla 1984; OUSE 1990). *I. binaculatus* Loman, 1902 - End.; Sil. (Rambla 1984). *I. flavopictus* Hirst, 1911 - End.; M. Sil. (OUSE 1990; *new data*: Mon Plaisir XII.93). *I. lomani* Hirst, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Rambla 1984). *Sitalcus incertus* Rambla, 1984 - End.; Sil. (Rambla 1984). *Miraceras pulchra* Rambla, 1984 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Rambla 1984). *Benoitinus elegans* Rambla, 1984 - End. gen.; Sil. (Rambla 1984), LD. *Biantes parvulus* (Hirst, 1911) - End.; M., Sil. (Rambla 1984).

ACARI

- Family HOLOTHYRIDAE '*Holothyrys niger*' Thon, 1906 - End.; Sil. (Thon 1906). '*H. seychellensis*' Thon, 1906 - End.; Sil. (Thon 1906). *Sternothyrys braueri* (Thon, 1906) - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Thon 1906).
- Family ORIBATIDAE *Hoplophthiracarus Afr.nus* Mahunka, 1984 - Afr.; Sil. (Mahunka 1984). *Li acarus piriformis* Warburton, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Warburton 1912). *Neolcodes rugosus* Warburton, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Warburton 1912) & P. *Notaspis 'clavipectinata'* - ?; Sil. (Warburton 1912). *N. impolita* Warburton, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Warburton 1912). *N. lamellicornis* Warburton, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Warburton 1912). *N. reticulata* Warburton, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Warburton 1912). *Oribata mammillata* Warburton, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Warburton 1912). *O. truncata* Warburton, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Warburton 1912). *Seychellozetes benoitii* Mahunka, 1984 - End.; Sil. (Mahunka 1984)

AMBLYPYGI

Family TARANTULIDAE *Charinus seychellarum* Krapelin, 1898 - End., M., Long, Sil. (Hirst 1913; Benoit 1979b), P. & Fel.

PEDIPALPI

Family SCHIZOMIDAE *Schizomus stultus* Hirst, 1913 - End., M., Long & Sil. (OUSE 1990)

PSEUDOSCORPIONES

Family ATEMNIIDAE *Anatemnus seychellesensis* Beier, 1940 - End., Sil. (Mahnert 1978) & Fel.

Family FAELLIDAE *Faella affinis* Hirst, 1913 - End., Sil. (Mahnert 1978; OUSE 1990), P. & LD.

Family GEOGARYPIDAE *Geogarypus ocellatus* Mahnert, 1978 - End., M., Sil. (Mahnert 1978; OUSE 1990), P. & Cur. *Oratemnus brevidigitatus* Beier, 1940 - End., M., Sil. (Mahnert 1978) & P.

SCORPIONES

Family SCORPIONIDAE *Lychas braueri* (Krapelin, 1896) - End., M., Sil. (Hirst 1913; OUSE 1990) & P.

UNIRAMIA

SYMPHYLA

Symphyla sp. - (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1994).

MYRIAPODA

CHILOPODA

Family SCUTIGERIDAE *Ballonema* sp. - End.?, M. & Sil. (Demange 1981; OUSE 1990 as *Scutigera* sp.)

Family GEOPHILIDAE *Mecistocephalus sechellarum* Demange, 1981 - End., Sil. (Demange 1981). *M. punctifrons* Newp., 1842 - End., M., Sil. (Demange 1981) & P.

Family SCOLOPENDRIDAE *Scotopendra subspinipes* Leach - Pantrop., M., Sil. (Demange 1981), P., A. & Freg. *Cryptops philomus* Attems, 1900 - End., M., Sil. (Demange 1981), P. & Cur.

Family LITHOBIDAE *Lithobius inflatitarsus* Eason, 1978 - End., M. & Sil. (Demange 1981). *L. sechellarum* Brölemann, 1896 - End., M. & Sil. (Demange 1981). *L. semperi* (Haase, 1887) - Asia; M. & Sil. (Demange 1981).

DIPLOPODA

Family CAMBALIDAE *Hypocambala anguina* (Attems, 1900) - End., M., Sil. (Attems 1900; Mauries 1980) & P.

Family HIRUDISOMIDAE *Rhinotus crassiceps* (Attems, 1900) - End., M. & Sil. (Attems 1900; Mauries 1980). *R. vanmoli* Mauries, 1980 - End., Sil. (Mauries 1980)

Family PARADOXOSOMIDAE *Pratinus planatus* Pocock, 1895 - End., M., Sil. (Mauries 1980) & P.

Family PYRGODESMIDAE *Propyrgodesmus* sp. - ?, M. & Sil. (Mauries 1980)

Family SIPHONOPHORIDAE *Pterozonium tropiphora* (Attems, 1900) - End., M., Sil. (Mauries 1980), P. & Freg. *Siphonophorella silhouettensis* Mauries, 1980 - End., Sil. (Mauries 1980).

Family SPHAEROTHERIDAE *Cyliosomella furciparum* (Brölemann, 1896) - End., M., Sil. (Mauries 1980) & Mar.

Family SPIROBOLLELLIDAE *Benoitulus flavicollis* Mauries, 1980 - End., M. & Sil. (new data, Gerlach pers. obs. 1996).

Family SPIROSTREPTIDAE *Charactopygus atratus* (Karsch, 1881) - End., M., Sil. (Mauries 1980) & LD. *Sechelleptus sechellarum* (Desjardius, 1834) - End. gen.; SA, V., Sil. (Mauries 1980), A., Cou., Couc., LD. & Freg.

Family TRICHOPOLYDESMIDAE *Cylindrodesmus hirsutus* (Pocock, 1888) - End., M., Sil. (Mauries 1980) & P.

Family TRIGONIULIDAE *Spiromanes sechellarum* Saussure & Zehntner, 1902 - End., Sil. (Mauries 1980) & A. *Spirostrophus narell* (Pocock, 1893) - End., M., Cerf, Sil. (Mauries

1980), P., Cur., LD. & Freg. *Spiromanes braueri* (Attems, 1900) - End., M. & Sil. (Mauries 1980).

HEXAPODA

THYSANURA

Family CAMPODEIDAE *Lepidocampa fimbriatipes* Carpenter, 1916 - End., M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916).

Family IAPYGIDAE *Iapyx silvestris* Carpenter, 1916 - End., M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916).

Family LEPISMIDAE *Lepidospora braueri* Escherich, 1904 - End., M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916).

Family MACHILIDAE *Corethromachilis brevipalpis* Carpenter, 1916 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916). *C. gardineri* Carpenter, 1916 - End., M., Sil. (Carpenter 1916) & P. C. *gibba* Carpenter, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916).

COLLEMBOLA

Family ENTOMOBRYIDAE *Acanthurella braueri* Börner, 1906 - End.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916). *Entomobrya seychellarum* Carpenter, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916). *Heteromuricus longicornis* Carpenter, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916). *Isotomurus obscurus* Carpenter, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916). *Lepidocyrtus imperialis* Carpenter, 1916 - End., M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916).

Family PODURIDAE *Neanura sexoculata* Carpenter, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Carpenter 1916).

ODONATA

Family AESCHNIDAE *Gynacantha stylata* Martin, 1896 - End.; Sil. (Campion 1913)

Family AGRIONIDAE *Allolestes maclachlani* Selys, 1869 - End., M., Sil. (Campion 1913) & P. A. *nigra* Martin, 1896 - End.; Sil. (Campion 1913). *Ceragrion glabrum* (Burm., 1839) - Afr.: Sil. (Campion 1913), P. & A. *Leptocnemis bilineata* (Selys, 1869) - End., M. & Sil. (Campion 1913).

Family COENAGRIONIDAE *Agriocnemis pygmaea* (Selys, 1877) - Asia; M., Sil. (Campion 1913), P., A. & LD. *Seychellibasis alluandi* (Martin, 1913) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Campion 1913)

Family LIBELLULIDAE *Diplacodes trivialis* (Ramb., 1842) - Asia; M., Sil. (Campion 1913), P. & A. *Orthetrum stemmale* (Selys, 1877) - Afr.; M., Cerf, Sil. (Campion 1913), P., Cou., Cauc., A., LD., Bird & Denis. *Trapezostigma limbata* (Desjardins, 1832); Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Campion 1913), P. & A.

Family PLATYCNEMIDIDAE *Leptocnemis cyanops* (Selys, 1869) - End.; M., Sil. (Campion 1913) & P.

ORTHOPTERA

Family ACRYDIIDAE *Ocyettix nymphula* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *O. pupulus* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *Coptotiggia cristata* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *Euschmidtia cruciformis* (Bolivar, 1895) - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *Rhynchotettix gardineri* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912).

Family ATYDIIDAE *Metioche bolivari* Chopard, 1968 - End.; Sil. (OUSE 1990).

Family GRILLIDAE *Acheta bimaculata* (Geer, 1773) - Afr.-Asia; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1912), P. & Bird. *Euscyrus bivittatus* Guerin, 1844 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *E. madagascariensis* Gorochoff, 1994 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Gorochoff 1994). *Gryllapterus tomentosus* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *Pentacentrus nigrifrons* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *Phaeogryllus fuscus* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *Phaloria insularis* (Bolivar, 1912) - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *Scottia salticiformis* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *Seychellestia longicercata* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *S. nitidula* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *S. patellifera* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *Trigonidium perpusillum* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *T. vittaticolle* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912).

Zarceus fallacinus Bolivar, 1895 - End., M., Long, Anon. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990).

Family MOGOPLISTIDAE *Ornebius elegantulus* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M., Long & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *O. succineus* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; Anon. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990 as *Ornebius* sp.)

Family PHASGONURIDAE *Conocephalus iris* (Serville, 1839) - Afr., M., Sil. (Bolivar 1912), P. & Denis. *Pelerinus rostratus* (Brunner, 1878) - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *Phisis visenda* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912). *Prosopogryllacris sechellensis* (Bolivar, 1895) - End.; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990) & P. *Odontolakis* cf. *sexpunctata* - Mad.; M. & Sil. (OUSE 1990). *Ruspolia nitidulus* (Scopoli, 1786) - Old World; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1912), P. & Denis.

Family PHASMIDAE *Carausius alluaudi* (Bolivar, 1895) - End.; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990), P. & LD. *C. gardineri* Bolivar, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990). *C. scotti* Ferriere, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Ferriere 1912; Matyot 1990). *C. sechellensis* (Bolivar, 1895) - End., M., Sil. (Bolivar 1912; OUSE 1990) & P. *Graeffea sechellensis* Ferriere, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Ferriere 1912) & P. *Phyllium bioculatum* Gray, 1832 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1912).

DICTYOPTERA

Family BLATTIDAE *Blatella similis* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *Desmosia alluaudi* Bolivar, 1895 - End. gen.; M., Long & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *Distichopsis stylopyga* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *Hololeptoblatta pandunicola* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *Lobopterella dimidiatipes* (Bouvier, 1890) - Asia; M., Long, Sil. (Bouvier 1924; Roth 1996) & A. *Margattea crassivenosa* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *M. longicercata* Bolivar, 1924 - Masc.; M., Long, Anon., Sil. (Bolivar 1924) & Bird. *Miriamrothschildia badia* (Bolivar, 1924) - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *M. biplagiata* (Bolivar, 1924) - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *M. gardineri* (Bolivar, 1924) - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *M. labyrinthica* (Bolivar, 1924) - End.; M. & Sil. (Roth 1996). *Panesthia angustipennis* (Illiger) - Asia; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1924 as *P. javanica*; Roth 1996) & P. *Periplaneta australasiae* (Fabricius, 1775) - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *Pycnoscelus 'surinamensis'* - Pantrop.; M., Long, Sil. (Bolivar 1924), P., A. LD., Bird & Denis. *Stiferia acuticercu* Bolivar, 1924 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1924; Roth 1996) & Fel. *S. depressiceps* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924; Roth 1996). *Theganopteryx lanulata* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1924) & Fel. *T. minuta* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924). *T. reticulata* Bolivar, 1924 - End.; M., Sil. (Bolivar 1924), P. & Fel.

Family MANTIDAE *Polyspilota aeruginosa* (Goeze, 1778) - Afr.-Asia; M. & Sil. (Bolivar 1924).

ISOPTERA

Family PROTERMITIDAE *Calotermes laticollis* Holmgren, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Holmgren 1910). *C. scotti* Holmgren, 1910 - End.; Sil. (Holmgren 1910).

DERMAPTERA

Family CARCINOPHORIDAE *Antisolabis scotti* (Burr, 1910) - End.; Sil. (Burr 1910; Brindle 1976, Floater 1994). *Euborellia annulipes* (Lucas) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Floater 1994), LD. & Freg.

Family LABIDURIDAE *Echinosoma bolivari* Rodzianko - Mad.; Sil. (Burr 1910). *Labidura riparia* (Pallas) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Floater 1994) & Freg.

Family LABIIDAE *Chaetotabia fryeri* (Burr, 1910) - End.; Sil. (Burr 1910; Brindle 1976). *Gonolabis electra* Burr - Introduced; M., Sil. (Floater 1994), P., Cur., A. & LD. *Labia curvicauda* (Motschulsky) - Cosmo, M. & Sil. (Burr 1910). *Marava arachidis* (Yersin) - Cosmo.; Sil. (Brindle 1976). *M. griveaudi* Brindle - Mad., Sil. (Burr 1910 & Floater 1994). *Spirolabia browni* (Hincks) - End.; M. & Sil. (Floater 1994).

Family SPONGIPHORIDAE *Chaetospania gardineri* (Burr, 1910) - End.; M. & Sil. (Burr 1910; Matyot 1995). *C. thoracica* (Dohrn) - Asia - M. & Sil. (Burr 1910).

HEMIPTERA

- Family ANTHOCORIDAE *Lasiochilus alluandi* Reut., 1893 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1913) & LD.
L. scotti Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Ostorodiasoldes typicus* Distant,
1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *O. signatus* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913).
Paralasiochilus piceus Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Sesellius paralletus*
(Motsch., 1863) - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family ARADIDAE *Neuroctenus caffer* (Stal, 1855) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Pictinus*
invalidus (Bergroth, 1894) - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1913). P. & LD.
- Family CAPSIDAE *Collaria improvisa* Reut., 1893 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Cylapus*
nigratorius Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Felisacus auritulus* Distant,
1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Fulvius pictus* Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant
1913). *F. niger* Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Lygus cinnamomeus*
Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *L. sanguineosignatus* Distant, 1913 - End.;
Sil. (Distant 1913). *L. silhouettensis* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913).
Megacaelum flagellatum Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *M. mimicum*
Distant, 1913 - End.; M., Long, Sil. (Distant 1913), P., Bird & Denis. *Prohoscidocoris*
pluto Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Sthenarusoides montanus* Distant,
1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family CERATOCOMBIDAE *Ceratocombus insularis* Reut., 1893 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1913) &
LD.
- Family CERCOPIDAE *Pytelus mahei* Distant, 1909 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family COCCIDAE *Lepidosaphes dupontii* Green, 1916 - End.?. Sil. (Green 1916).
- Family COREIDAE *Acanthomia horrida* (Germ., 1837) - Afr.; M., Long & Sil. (Distant 1913).
Corizus scotti Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Leptocorisla apicalis* Westwood,
1842 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Serinetha toricollis* Bergroth, 1893 - End.; M., Sil.
(Distant 1913) & Fel. *Stenocephalus punctipes* Stal, 1873 - Mad., M., Long, Sil. (Distant
1913), P., Bird & Denis.
- Family FULGORIDAE *Adolendana typica* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916).
Aquaellium brunnescens Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *A. elegantulum*
Distant, 1916 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & Fel. *A. typicum* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. &
Sil. (Distant 1916). *Armitulstrum gardineri* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916).
Aselgeoides insularis Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Brixia stellata*
Distant, 1916 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & P. *Caneirona maculipennis* Distant, 1916 -
End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & P. *Carmentalla biformis* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil.
(Distant 1916). *Clusivius spectabilis* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916).
Consualia robusta Distant, 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *Fescennia aurea* Distant, 1916
- End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Flatoides protea* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant
1916). *Fordicidia robusta* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Igvium*
albomaculatum Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Ivinga typica* Distant, 1909
- Ald.; M., Anon., Sil. (Distant 1916), P., Fel., Mar., Denis. *Ketumala rubromarginata*
Distant, 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *Nesoprivesa fuscovaria* Distant, 1916 - Ald.; M.,
Anon. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Nisia atrovenosa* (Leth., 1888) - Asia; M., Sil. (Distant 1916),
P. & Fel. *N. fuscofasciata* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *N. thoracica*
Distant, 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *Opiconsiva colorata* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. &
Sil. (Distant 1916). *O. fuscovaria* Distant, 1916 - End.; M., Anon., Sil. (Distant 1916) &
Mar. *O. insularis* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Osaka hyalina* Distant,
1909 - Ald.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Parakosalya insularis* Distant, 1916 - End.; Sil.
(Distant 1916). *Privesana infusca* (Distant, 1909) - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & P.
Privesa melanaria Distant, 1916 - End.; Long & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Ugyops facialis*
Distant, 1916 - Ald.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *U. senescens* Distant, 1909 - Ann.; M., Sil.
(Distant 1916) & P. *Volcanalla atrovarya* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *V.*
capitata Distant, 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *V. designata* Distant, 1916 - End.; Sil.
(Distant 1916). *V. fumosa* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *V. modesta*
Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *V. picturata* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil.
(Distant 1916). *V. uniformis* Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *V. varicolor*
Distant, 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916).

- Family HYDROMETRIDAE *Gerris cereiventris* Sign., 1862 - Masc.; M., Sil (Distant 1913) & P. *G. dolosa* (Bergroth, 1893) - Ami., M., Long, Sil. (Distant 1913) & LD *Hydrometra ambulator* Stal, 1855 - Afr.; M. & Sil (Distant 1913).
- Family JASSIDAE *Aeropona prasina* (Walker, 1858) - Asia, M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & P. *Baletutha chersonisia* Distant 1916 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *B. varicolor* Distant 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Bythoscopus indicus* (Leth., 1892) - Asia; Sil. (Distant 1916). *Ildiocerus scotti* Distant, 1916 - End., M., Sil. (Distant 1916). P & Fel. *Jassus indicus* (Walker, 1851) - Asia, M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Kolla funeralis* Distant 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Maiestas illustris* Distant 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Matsumurana facialis* Distant 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *Nehela aterrima* Distant 1916 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & Fel. *N. bimaculicollis* (Satl, 1855) - Afr.-Asia, M., Anon. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *N. elegantula* Distant 1916 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1916) & P. *N. flavolineata* Distant 1916 - End., M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *N. lineoligera* Distant 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *Paralimnux silhouettensis* Distant 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *Scaphoideus seychellensis* Distant 1916 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1916). *S. tessellatus* Distant 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916). *S. vagans* Distant 1916 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1916).
- Family LYGAEIDAE *Aphanus consocialis* Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Cligenes gardineri* Distant, 1913 - End., M., Sil. (Distant 1913), P & Fel. *Dieuches annulatus* (Sign., 1890) - Mad; M., Sil. (Distant 1913), Bird & Denis. *D. cardui* Distant, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Distant 1913) & P. *D. placidus* (Stal, 1865) - Masc.; M., Sil. (Distant 1913), P. & Denis. *Lachnophorus albidomaculatus* Distant, 1913 - Ald., M., Sil. (Distant 1913) & Bird. *Ninus sechellensis* Bergroth, 1893 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Nystius albipennis* Distant, 1913 - Ald.; M., Long & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Pamera sladeni* Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *P. vineta* Say, 1831 - Cosmo.; M., Long & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Paromius seychellensis* (Walker, 1872) - Asia; M., Long & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family MARGARODIDAE *Icerya sechellarum* (Westwood, 1855) - Cosmo.; M., Sil. (Green 1907; OUSE 1990), P. & A.
- Family NABIDAE *Acanthobrachys elegantula* (Stal, 1865) - Masc.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family NEPIDAE *Ranatra grandocula* Bergroth, 1893 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family NOTONECTIDAE *Anisops varius* Fieb., 1851 - Afr.-Asia; M., Sil. (Distant 1913) & P.
- Family PENTATOMIDAE *Amirantca gardineri* Distant, 1909 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Bathycaelia praelongiorstris* Bergroth, 1893 - Ami.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Geotomus proximus* Sign., 1883 - Masc.; M., Sil. (Distant 1913), P., LD., Bird & Denis. *Nezara heegeri* (Fieb., 1861) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *N. spicata* Distant, 1913 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Sepina seychellensis* Distant, 1909 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family REDUVIIDAE *Calphurnioides elongatus* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Henicocephalus* sp. - ?; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Luteva malayana* Distant, 1903 - Asia; M., Long, Sil. (Distant 1913) & Fel. *Nagusta naura* Distant, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Oncocephalus sordidus* Stal, 1855 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Ploiariola scotti* Distant, 1913 - End.; M., Long & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Polytoxus modestus* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Quinssyano funeralis* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Q. varicolor* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Rochonia galeatus* Distant, 1913 - End., Sil. (Distant 1913). *Stenolaemus madagascariensis* (Westwood, 1844) - Mad.; Sil. (Distant 1913).
- Family TINGIIDAE *Dulinius nigrolineatus* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913)
- Family VELIIDAE *Microvelia repentina* Distant, 1904 - End.; M. & Sil. (Distant 1913). *Picautia pronotalis* Distant, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Distant 1913). *Rhagovelia nigricans* (Burm., 1835) - Afr.-Asia; M., Sil. (Distant 1913) & P.

PSOCOPTERA

- Family CAECILIIDAE *Caecilius crassicornis* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *C. inbecillus* McLachlan, 1866 - Masc.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *C. interruptus* Enderlein, 1908 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *C. prostratus* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *C. seychellensis* Enderlein, 1931 - End., M. & Sil.

(Enderlein 1931). *C. vau* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *C. vaov* Enderlein, 1931 - End. M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Ectopsocus ferrugineiceps* Enderlein, 1907 - End.; M. & Sil. (1929). *Kolbea fenestriflora* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 19129). *Pseudococcilius brevicornis* Enderlein, 1929 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 19129). *Peripsocus reichertii* Enderlein, 1903 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Scottiella compta* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931).

Family EMPHERIIDAE *Empheriella denervosa* Enderlein, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931).

Family LEPIDOPSCOIDEAE *Echmepteryx acutipennis* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *E. asculanus* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *E. hieroglyphica* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *E. maculimargo* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Lepidopsocus nepticulides* Enderlein, 1903 - End.; M., Long & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *L. ochreus* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Loxopholia annuliflora* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *L. hebes* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *L. pinnula* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Ptenocorium alutaceum* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Thylacopsis madagascariensis* (Kolbe, 1885) - Mad.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *T. mahensis* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *T. monticola* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *T. psyche* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *T. scotti* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931).

Family MYOPSOCIDAE *Rhaptoneura muscosa* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Phlotodes lichenosa* Enderlein, 1931 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931).

Family PSOCIDAE *Anopistoscaena specularifrons* Enderlein, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931). *Hemipsocus Afr. nus* Enderlein, 1907 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1931).

THYSANOPTERA

Family IDOLOTHRIPIDAE *Dicalothrips hystrix* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *D. rex* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *D. seychellensis* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bagnall 1921).

Family PHLAETHRIPIDAE *Acallurothrips proturus* Bagnall, 1921 - End. gen.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *Caenurothrips validus* Bagnall, 1921 - End. gen.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *Cryptothrips difficilis* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *Gynaikothrips scotti* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *Haplothrips silhouettensis* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *Liothrips intrepidus* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921). *L. nigricornis* Bagnall, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bagnall 1921).

Family THRIPIDAE *Thrips* sp. - Sil. (Bagnall 1921).

SIPHONAPTERA

Family CTENOCEPHALIDAE *Ctenocephalus felis* (Bouche, 1835) - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Scott 1914)

NEUROPTERA

Family CONIOPTERYGIDAE *Semidalis africana* Enderlein, 1906 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1910).

Family HEMEROBIIDAE *Micromus timidus* Hagen, 1853 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1910).

Family MYRMELEONIDAE *Myrmeleon obscurus* Rambur, 1853 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Needham, 1914) & Bird.

LEPIDOPTERA

Family ALUCTITIDAE *Alucita seychellensis* (Fletcher, 1910) - End.; M. & Sil. (Fletcher 1910).

Family ARCTIIDAE *Argina cribraria* (Clerk, 1759) - Palaeotrop.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Mahensia seychellarum* Fryer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Nyctemera seychellensis* (Hampson, 1908) - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965). *Philenora subfusca* Fryer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Utetheisa elata* (Fabricius, 1798) - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *U. pulchelloides* Hampson, 1901 - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912), L.D. & Bird.

Family BLASTOBASIDAE *Blastobasis acarta* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

- Family COSMOPTERYGIDAE *Stigmatophora hieroglypta* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *S. ilarcha* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *S. tentoria* Meyrick, 1911 - Chugos; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).
- Family CRAMBIDAE *Crambus auronivellus* Fryer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *C. seychellensis* Fletcher, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fletcher 1910). *Culladia admigratella* (Walker, 1863) - Palaeotrop.; M., SA., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & P. *Diptychophora muscella* Fryer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912).
- Family DANALIDAE *Euploea nitra* Moore, 1857 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912), P & LD.
- Family EPERMENIIDAE *Epermenia* sp. - ?; Sil. (Floater 1993).
- Family EPIPLEMIDAE *Dirades theclata* (Guenee, 1852) - Palaeotrop.; M., Long & Sil. (Fryer 1912).
- Family GALLERIIDAE *Lamoria anella* (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) - Cosmo.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965).
- Family GELICHIIDAE *Brachmia cricopa* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Chaliniastis chromatica* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Lecithocera effera* Meyrick, 1918 - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Onebala cubiculata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Thotricha fridaella* Legrand, 1958 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *T. tenuis* (Walsingham, 1891) - Afr.; M., Cerf & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).
- Family GEOMETRIDAE *Chloroclystis nigella* (Joannis, 1906) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1996). *Comostolopsis stadeni* Prout, 1915 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912 as *Comostola laesaria*). *Gymnoscelis tenera* Warren, 1901 - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Fel. *Ozola inexcisata* Fryer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Scopula minorata* (Boisduval, 1833) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965), P., Frog. & Bird. *Thalassodes antithetica* Herbulot, 1964 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965).
- Family GLYPHPTERYGIDAE *Glyphipteryx dichalina* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *G. medica* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1996).
- Family HELIODINIDAE *Calicotis animula* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Epicroesa* sp. - End.; Sil. (Floater, 1995) & A.
- Family HESPERIIDAE *Borbo gemella* (Boisduval, 1834) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965) & P. *Eagris sabadius* (Gray, 1832) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912).
- Family HYBLAEIDAE *Hyblaea puera* (Cramer, 1777) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Legrand 1965) & P.
- Family LITHOCOLLETIDAE *Acrocercops martaella* Legrand, 1965 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *A. pentuplaca* Meyrick, 1911 - Ami., M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Cuphodes luxuriosa* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *C. tridora* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911).
- Family LYCAENIDAE *Lampides boeticus* (Linnaeus, 1767) - Cosmo.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Zizeeria knysna* (Trimen, 1862) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912), P., Bird & Denis. *Zizula hylax* (Fabricius, 1775) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965).
- Family LYMANTHRIDAE *Porthesia pectinata* Fryer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Fryer 1912).
- Family LYONETHIDAE *Decadorchis methodica* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *D. molynta* Meyrick, 1911 - Ami., M., Anon., Sil. (Meyrick 1911), P. & Bird. *Ereunetis calyptra* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *E. scaligera* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Lyonetia probolactis* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Ogopona cyanodesma* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. daubanelia* Legrand, 1958 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *O. ensifera* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. fricata* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. hellogramma* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. hermatias* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M., Anon., Sil. (Meyrick 1911) & Fel. *O. ichnora* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. irenica* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. lactiflua* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. nephalla* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. phaeochalca* (Meyrick, 1908) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. rhothiaula* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. sacchari* (Bojer, 1856) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Meyrick 1911) & A. *O. selecta* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. sultana* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. tarsota* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Oinophila crobylora* Meyrick, 1911 -

End., Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. glomerata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *O. rorida* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Orthochotha rhodothicta* (Meyrick, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

Family METACHANDRIDAE *Metachanda autocentra* Meyrick, 1911 - End., Sil. (Meyrick 1911) & Fel. *M. classica* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. columnata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. crypsitricha* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. fortunata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. fumata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911) & Fel. *M. glacata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. hydraula* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. miltospila* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. noctivaga* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. prodelta* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911) & Fel. *M. thaleropsis* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *M. trixantha* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Chanyasis botanodes* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *C. cyrtopa* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

Family NOCTUIDAE *Achaea mercatoria* (Fabricius, 1775) - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Anticarsia irrorata* (Fabricius, 1781) - Palaetrop.; M., SA., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965). P. & Freg. *Arrade erebusalis* Walker, 1863 - Asia; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *A. massalis* Swinhoe, 1885 - Asia; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Bocana* sp. - ?; Sil. (Floater 1993). *Callopietria mallardi* (Guenee, 1863) - Afr.; M., R., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Freg. *C. yerburi* (Butler, 1884) - Palaetrop.; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Cosmophila flava* (Fabricius, 1775) - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Dragana pansalis* Walker, 1858 - Palaetrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912), P. & Fel. *Dysgonia torrida* (Guenee, 1852) - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Heliothis armigera* (Hübner, 1808) - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1996). *Hypena consocialis* Walker, 1865 - Palaetrop.; M., Cerf. Sil. (Fryer 1912), P. & Freg. *H. masuralis* Guenee, 1854 - Palaetrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912), P. & Freg. *H. strigata* (Fabricius, 1798) - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *H. variabilis* Walker, 1865 - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Leucania continentalis* Berio, 1962 Afr.; M., Sil. (Legrand 1965) & P. *Mocis repanda* (Fabricius, 1794) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & P. *Nanaguna breviscula* Walker, 1863 - Asia; M. & Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1996). *Oruza rupestre* Fryer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Parsadena beauvaltonensis* Legrand, 1965 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Chrysodeixis chalytes* (Esper, 1789) - Palaetrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965; Floater 1993). Mar. & Bird. *P. umbirena* Guenee, 1852 - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1996). *Polydesmu umbricola* Boisduval, 1833 - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Rivula dimorpha* Fryer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Simplicia extinctalis* (Zeller, 1852) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Stictopora antemarginata* (Saalmüller, 1891) - Mad.; M., Sil. (Legrand 1965) & Fel. *Trigonodes hypasia* (Cramer, 1779) - Afr.; M., SA., Cerf. Sil. (Fryer 1912), P., Fel. & Freg.

Family NYMPHALIDAE *Hypollunas misippus* (Linnaeus, 1764) - Indo-Pacific; M., SA., Sil. (Legrand 1965), N., & P. *Phalanta philiberti* (Joannis, 1893) - End.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & P.

Family PHYCITIDAE *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832) - Pantrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965).

Family PTEROPHORIDAE *Crombrugghia wahlbergi* (Zeller, 1852) - Palaetrop.; M. & Sil. (new data: Gerlach pers. obs. 1996). *Exelastis punilio* (Zeller, 1873) - Pantropical; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Platyptilia 'ciropleura'* - ?; Sil. (Floater 1993). *P. claripicta* Fletcher, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fletcher, 1910). *P. dimorpha* Fletcher, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fletcher 1910). *P. pusillidactyla* (Walker, 1864) - Pantropical; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965).

Family PLUTELLIDAE *Argyresthia lustralis* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

Family PHYCITIDAE *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832) - Pantrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Phycita pectinicornella* Fryer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *P. transobliquella* Legrand, 1965 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965).

Family PYRALIDAE *Herpetogramma licarsialis* Walker - Palaetrop.; Sil. (Floater 1993).

Hypsopygia mauritialis (Boisduval, 1833) - Palaetrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Bird.

Family PYRAUSTIDAE *Antiercta ornatalis* (Duponchel, 1832) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965), P., Fel. & Denis. *Bradina aurcolalis* Joannis, 1894 - End.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Floater undated) & P. *Diaphana dupontii* (Joannis, 1916) - Palaetrop.; M.,

Long, Sil. (Legrand 1965), Mar., Fel. & Denis. *D. indica* (Saunders, 1851) - Palaetotrop.; M., Sil. (Legrand 1965), P., Mar., Freg. & Birt. *D. sinuata* (Fabricius, 1781) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965). *Eurhynchopodes tricoloralis* (Zeller, 1852) - Palaetotrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912), P. & Denis. *Hedylepta indicata* (Fabricius, 1775) - Pantrop.; M., SA., Sil. (Fryer 1912), Bird & Denis. *Marasmiu poeyalis* (Boisduval, 1833) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *M. trapezalis* Guenee, 1854 - Palaetotrop.; M., Cerf, Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Freg. *M. trebiusalis* (Walker, 1859) - Palaetotrop.; M., Cerf, Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Bird. *Nacoleia niphralis* (Walker, 1859) - Palaetotrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Freg. *Noorda amethystina* (Swinhoe, 1894) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Omphisa anastomosalis* (Guenee, 1854) - Asia; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Pulpita unionalis* (Hubner, 1796) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Pionea abactis* (Walker, 1859) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Psara frenetialis* Legrand, 1965 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *P. mahensis* (Fletcher, 1910) - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *P. phaeopteralis* (Guenee, 1854) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & P. *Pyrausta mahensis* Fletcher, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Sufetula minimalis* Fletcher, 1910 - Am.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Fel. *Stemorrhages sericea* (Drury, 1770) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965) & P. *Synclera univocalis* (Walker, 1859) - Asia; M., SA., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965), Fel. & Denis. *Syngamia abruptalis* (Walker, 1859) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Stemorrhages sericea* (Drury, 1770) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965) & P. *Udea martialis* (Guenee, 1854) - Palaetotrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912) & P.

Family SATYRIDAE *Melanitis leda* (Drury) - Palaetotrop.; M., Sil. (Fryer 1912; Legrand 1965) & N.

Family SPHINGIDAE *Acherontia atropos* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (new data; Gerluch pers. obs. 1990). *Cephonodes hylas* (Linnaeus, 1771) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *Herse convolvuli* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Palaetotrop.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Hippotion eson* (Cramer, 1779) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912; Floater 1993). *Nephela leighi* Joicey & Talbot, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912). *Tennora fumosa* (Walker, 1856) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Fryer 1912).

Family THYRIDIDAE *Rhodoneura apicale* Fryer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Fryer 1912). *R. tibiale* Fryer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Fryer 1912) & Mar.

Family TINEIDAE *Mastigostoma gypsatma* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Oinophila crobylora* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Progonarma pagetodes* Meyrick, 1911 - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Scardia lochoea* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Sporadathra sicaria* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Tinea coronata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *T. millichopa* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *T. pachyspila* Meyrick, 1905 - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *T. saucropis* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Legrand 1965). *T. trochoea* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

Family TORTRICIDAE *Adoxophyes ergatica* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Argyroptoe conchopleura* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *A. hygrantis* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *A. leucaspis* Meyrick, 1902 - Introduced?; Sil. (Meyrick 1911) & Fel. *Bactra legitima* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Herpystis rusticula* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Eucosma temenitis* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Platypeplus aprobola* (Meyrick, 1886) - Indo-Pacific; M. & Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

Family XYLORECTIDAE *Paraclada tricapna* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911). *Anachastis digitata* Meyrick, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Meyrick 1911).

TRICHOPTERA

Family ECNOMIDAE *Ecnomus insularis* Ulmer, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Ulmer 1910).

DIPTERA

Family AGROMYZIDAE *Agromyza candidipennis* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *A. funebris* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *A. similis* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Lencopsis griseola* (Fallen, 1823) - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).

Family BORBORIDAE *Limosina curvinervis* Stenhammer, 1853 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Colln 1912). *L. punctipennis* (Wiedemann, 1830) - Pantrop.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Colln 1912).

- Family CECIDOMYIIDAE: *Clinodiplosis insularum* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1911). *C. scotti* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1911). *Lepidodiplosis filipes* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1911).
- Family CERATOPOGONIIDAE: *Atrichopogen lampronotus* (Kieffer, 1911) - End., M., Sil. (Kieffer 1911) & Fel. *Bezzia rufipes* (Kieffer, 1911) - Erd.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1911). *Ceratopogon fallenellus* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1911). *C. lasianotus* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; M., Sil. (Kieffer 1911), Fel. & Bird. *Serromyia festiva* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1911).
- Family CHIRONOMIDAE: *Trichocladius quadrifasciatus* Kieffer, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1911).
- Family CHLOROPIDAE: *Gaurax seychellensis* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Meroscinis aeneifrons* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Notanulax trisulcata* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Oscinis colorata* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *O. complicata* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914) & P.
- Family CULICIDAE: *Aedes albopictus* (Skuse, 1895) - Indo-Pacific; widespread - Sil. (Theobald 1912; new data: pers. obs., 1990-6). *Culex scottii* Theobald, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Theobald 1912). *Pseudofalcidia nepenthes* Theobald, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Theobald 1912; new data: pers. obs., 1990). *Reedomyia seychellensis* Theobald, 1912 - Ald., M., Sil. (Theobald 1912) & Denis.
- Family DOLICHOPODIDAE: *Amblypsilopus pallidicornis* (Grimshaw, 1901) - Pacific; M., Sil. (Lamb 1922) & P. *Chrysotus seychellensis* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Mascaronomyia amplicaudata* (Lamb, 1922) - End.; Sil. (Lamb 1922). *M. grandicaudata* (Lamb, 1922) - End.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1922) & P. *M. indistincta* (Lamb, 1922) - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Paracleius solitarius* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Pipunculus semtopacus* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *P. syriaticoides* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Psilopus bilobatus* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1922), Fel. & Denis. *P. lasiophthalmus* Lamb, 1922 - End.; Long & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *P. magnicaudatus* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Urodolichus caudatus* Lamb, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922).
- Family DROSOPHILIDAE: *Drosophila aberrans* Lamb, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *D. finitima* Lamb, 1914 - S.Afr.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *D. nasuta* Lamb, 1914 - Afr., Mad.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914) & Fel. *D. similis* Lamb, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914) & Fel. *D. simulans* Sturtevant - Afr.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914) & Fel. *D. spinipes* Lamb, 1914 - Afr.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914) & P. *D. triangulifer* Lamb, 1914 - Afr., M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Leucophenga grossipalpis* (Lamb, 1914) - End., M., Long, Sil. (Lamb 1914), P. & Fel. *L. sericea* (Lamb, 1914) - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Zaprionus vittiger* Coquillett, 1902 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).
- Family EMPIDIDAE: *Syndax nitida* Loew. - Afr.-Asia; Sil. (Collin 1922). *Paralybos iridipennis* Kertész - SE.Asia; Sil. (Collin 1922). *Tachydromia lacteisetata* Collin, 1922 - End.; Sil. (Collin 1922).
- Family EPHYDRIDAE: *Allotrichoma argentipraetexta* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Collin 1922).
- Family HETERONEURIDAE: *Heteromeria nigrifrons* Lamb, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *H. plumicornis* Lamb, 1914 - End.; Anon. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).
- Family LONCHAEIDAE: *Lonchaea plumata* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Long, Anon. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *L. vibrissifer* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).
- Family MICROPEZIDAE: *Nereus althaudi* Giglio-Tos, 1895 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).
- Family MELICHIDAE: *Desmometopa inauratum* Lamb, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).
- Family MUSCIDAE: *Dichaetomyia fasciculifera* (Stein, 1910) - End., M., Sil. (Stein 1910). Floater (1995) & Fel. *Limnophora fasciolata* Stein, 1910 - End.; M., Long & Sil. (Stein 1910). *Musca domestica* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Cosmo.; M., Sil. (Stein 1910) & Denis. *Mydaea compressipalpis* Stein, 1910 - End.; M., Long & Sil. (Stein 1910). *M. mediana* Stein, 1910 - End.; M., Long, Sil. (Stein 1910) & P.
- Family MYCETOPHILIDAE: *Ceratosciara coniculatea* Enderlein, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1912). *Sciara bifurcata* Enderlein, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1912). *S. divergens* Enderlein, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1912). *S. mahensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M.,

- Anon. & Sil. (Enderlein 1912). *S. nigriceps* Enderlein, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1912). *S. rimiscutellata* Enderlein, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Enderlein 1912)
- Family ORTALIDAE *Plagiostenoptera cyanosoma* Hendel, 1912 - Ald.; M. & Sil. (Hendel in Lamb 1914). *P. ruficeps* Hendel, 1912 - Ald.; Long & Sil. (Hendel in Lamb 1914). *Chrysonyza azurea* Hendel, 1912 - Chagos; M., Long & Sil. (Hendel in Lamb 1914).
- Family PHORIDAE *Aphiochaeta consuta* Collin, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Collin 1912). *A. egena* Collin, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Collin 1912). *A. innocens* Collin, 1912 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Collin 1912). *A. limbata* Brues, 1905 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Collin 1912). *A. planipes* Collin, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Collin 1912). *A. soluta* Collin, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Collin 1912). *Chonocephalus similis* Brues, 1905 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Collin 1912)
- Family PSYCHODIDAE *Brunettia indica* Eaton, 1913 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Eaton 1913).
- Family SAPROMYZIDAE *Homoneura atra* Lamb, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Lamb 1914). *H. pulchrifrons* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914) & P. *H. varifrons* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Pachycerina obscuripennis* Lamb, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Lamb 1914). *P. seychellensis* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Long & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Sapromyza funebriicornis* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Long, Anon. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *S. nuduscula* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *S. striata* Lamb, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1914), P. & Fel.
- Family SEPSIDAE *Sepsis rufa* Macq., 1850 - Asia; M., Anon. & Sil. (Lamb 1914)
- Family STRATIOMYIIDAE *Cephalochrysa hovax* (Big., 1859) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Kertész 1912). *Lophoteles plumula* Loew, 1858 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kertész 1912). *Sargus seychellensis* Kertész, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Kertész 1912) & Mar.
- Family SYRPHIDAE *Eristalodes seychellarum* Bezzi, 1923 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Melanostoma annulipes* Macquart, 1850 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1922). *Volucella obesa* Fabricius - Cosmo.; M., Sil. (Lamb 1922) & P. *Xanthogramma aegyptium* Wiedemann - Afr.; M., Long & Sil. (Lamb 1922)
- Family TABANIDAE *Bouvierella inornata* Austen, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Austen 1920)
- Family TACHINIDAE *Actia spoliata* Bezzi, 1923 - End.; M., Sil. (Bezzi 1923) & Mar. *Exorista nemorilloides* Bezzi, 1923 - End.; Sil. (Bezzi 1923). *Lucilia cyanomarginata* Macquart, 1850 - Asia; M., Sil. (Bezzi 1923) & Denis. *Rhinia scotti* Stein, 1910 - Ald.; M. & Sil. (Stein 1910). *Sarcophaga spilargyra* Bezzi, 1923 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bezzi 1923)
- Family TIPULIDAE *Dicranomyia tipulipes* Karsch, 1886 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Edwards 1912). *Limnobia rhizosena* Speiser, 1909 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Edwards 1912). *Mesocypbona albicapitello* Edwards, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Edwards 1912). *M. maculosa* Edwards, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Edwards 1912). *Ormosia perpusilla* Edwards, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Edwards 1912). *Styrimomyia annulipes* Enderlein, 1912 - Mad.; M., Sil. (Edwards 1912) & Denis. *Thrypticomyla seychellensis* Edwards, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Edwards 1912)
- Family TRYPETIDAE *Acidia seychellensis* Lamb, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Oxyina sororcula* Wiedland, 1830 - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914). *Rhabdochaeta spinosa* Lamb, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Lamb 1914).

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- Family ANDRENIDAE *Halticus mahensis* Cameron, 1907 - End.; M., Long, Anon., Sil. (Cockerell 1912), P. & Denis. *Sphecodes scotti* Cockerell, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Cockerell 1912).
- Family APIDAE *Apis unicolor* Latreille, 1804 - Afr.; M., Long & Sil. (Cockerell 1912).
- Family BELYTIDAE *Belyta exsul* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Kieffer 1912) & P. *Leptorhaptus heteropus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Kieffer 1912) & P. *L. insulanus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Pantoclis insulanus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *P. scotti* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *P. seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Xenotoma insularis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912).
- Family BETHYLIDAE *Parasierola rostrata* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Pristocera crucifera* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Kieffer 1912) & P. *Scleroderma seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912).
- Family CERAPHRONIDAE *Conostigmus seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912)
- Family CHALCIDAE *Achrysocharis cardigaster* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Allotriozeon seychellense*

Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917) *Anacryptus insidiosus* Masi, 1917 - Indian Ocean; M., Anon. & Sil (Masi 1917) *Aximopsis elegans* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil (Masi 1917) & P. *Chalcis lepida* Masi, 1917 - End.; M., Anon., Sil. (Masi 1917) & Denis. *C. sodalis* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Cratolephus niger* Masi, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Masi 1917) & Fel. *Decatoma kestraneura* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Dinarmolaelaps protus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Dipara rufescens* Masi, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Masi 1917) & Fel. *Elasmus bellus* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil (Masi 1917). *Elasmus* sp. - End?; M & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Eucomys infelix* Masi, 1917 - Europe. M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Eupelmoides obscuratus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Euplectrus bicolor* (Swederus, 1795) - Europe; M., S.I. (Masi 1917) & P. *Eurytoma* sp. Masi, 1917 - End?; Sil (Masi 1917). *Eurytomidia dubia* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil (Masi 1917). *Gonatocerus silhouettae* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Habrolepis aeruginosa* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil (Masi 1917). *Leodanus onustus* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Metacatoser frequens* Masi, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Masi 1917) & P. *Micromelus affinis* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Neosciatheras laticeps* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Parageniaspis macrocerus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M & Sil (Masi 1917). *Paranastatus egregius* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *P. violaceus* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Podagrion terebrator* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Polynema seychellense* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Pseudanastatus crassicornis* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Sphegigastrella flavipes* Masi, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Masi 1917) & P. *S. longigastra* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Stenelachistus impressus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Stilbula lissoma* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Symphycus aphycoides* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Symplesomorpha ornata* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Syntomosphyrum trichops* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *S. modesta* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *S. pulchella* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *Tetrastichus dolichocerus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *T. hagenowii* (Ratzeburg, 1852) - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *T. inunctus* (Nees, 1834) - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *T. longiventris* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *T. metalliferus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *T. nigriceps* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917). *T. theoneurus* Masi, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Masi 1917). *Zeteticontus xanthopus* Masi, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Masi 1917).

Family CYNIPIDAE *Ectolyta atriceps* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil (Kieffer 1912). *Eucoila seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil (Kieffer 1912). *Gronotoma seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912).

Family DRYINIDAE *Labeo saxetanus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912).

Family EUMENIDAE *Eumenes alluaudi* Perez 1895 - End.; M., Sil. (Meade Waldo 1912), P. & Denis. *Odynerus seychellensis* Dall Torre 1904 - Masc.; M., Sil (Meade Waldo 1912) & P.

Family FORMICIDAE *Brachymyrmex corderoyi* Forel, 1895 - Introduced; M., Isl., Sil (Forel 1912) P., CS., Cou. & GS. *Camponotus grandidieri* Forel, 1886 - Afr.; M., Sil. (Forel 1912), P., CS., Cou., A., Alb., PS. & Freg. *C. hova* Forel, 1891 - Mad.; M., Sil (Forel 1912 as *C. maculatus*) & P. *C. thomasseti* Forel, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Forel 1912). *Cardiocondyla emeryi* Forel, 1881 - Cosmo.; M., Arion., Sil. (Forel 1912), GS. & PS. *Crematogaster rasoherinae* Forel, 1891 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Forel 1912). *Monomorium fossulatum* Emery, 1894 - Asia, Aust.; Sil. (Forel 1912) & Mar. *Paratrechina mixta* (Forel, 1897) - End.; M., Sil. (Forel 1912) & P. *Pheidole punctulata* Mayr, 1866 - Afr.; M., Long. Ro., Sil. (Forel 1912), A., Mar., GS., LD. & Bird. *Plagiolepis alluaudi* Emery, 1894 - Old World; M., Sil. (Forel 1912) & Fel. *P. madecassa* Forel, 1892 - Mad.; M., Anon., Sil. (Forel 1912), P. & A. *Solenopsis seychellensis* Forel, 1909 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Forel 1912). *Strumigenys scotti* Forel, 1912 - Afr.; Sil. (Forel 1912). *Tapinoma melanocephalum* (Fabricius, 1793) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Forel 1912), P., Cou., coue., A., GS. & PS. *Technomyrmex albipes* (Smith, 1861) - Introduced; widespread - Sil. (Forel 1912); OUSF 1990). *T. foreli* Emery, 1893 - Afr.; M., Long & Sil. (Forel 1912). *Terataner scotti* (Forel, 1912) - End.; Sil (Forel 1912) & P. *Tetramorium lanuginosum* Mayr, 1870 - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Forel 1912 as *Triglyphothrix stiatidensis*), A. & Fel. *Tetraponea rufonigra* (Jerdon,

1851) - Introduced?; Sil. (Forel 1912). *Vollenhovia laevithorax* Emery, 1894 - Asia; Sil. (Forel 1912) & P. *V. pirooskai* Forel, 1912 - Asia; Sil. (Forel 1912).

Family ICHNEUMONIDAE *Cremastrus punctus* Morley, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Morley 1912). *Dicolus equatorius* Morley, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Morley 1912). *Diocetes vulgaris* Morley, 1912 - Asia; M., Sil. (Morley 1912) & P. *Eclythromorpha rufa* Cameron, 1907 - End.; M. & Sil. (Morley 1912). *Hemiteles cingulatorius* Morley, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Morley 1912) & P. *Tarytia minuta* Morley, 1912 - End., M. & Sil. (Morley 1912). *Thersilochus evanescens* Morley, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Morley 1912).

Family MEGACHILIDAE *Megachile seychellensis* Cameron 1907 - Ald., M., Long, Sil. (Cockerell 1912) & P.

Family PLATYGASTERIDAE *Amblyaspis flavosignatus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Platygaster seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912).

Family POMPLIIDAE *Mygymia nenitra* Saussier - Mad.; Sil. (Turner 1911).

Family SCELIONIDAE *Baesus curvatus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Diapria saxatilis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Kieffer 1912) & P. *D. scotti* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *D. seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Enneascelio exaratus* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Hadronotus saxatilis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Lunproteleia heterocera* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *L. pulchripennis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Loxotropa exsul* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *L. semirufa* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Microteleia versicolor* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Neuroteleia heterocera* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Oriscello seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Paranteris flaviclava* Kieffer, 1912 - End. gen., M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *P. nigriceps* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *P. nigriclava* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Kieffer 1912) & Fel. *P. striatigena* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Paratrimorus atriceps* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Psiloteleia atra* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Rhopalopria vulgaris* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Schizopria flaviclava* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; Sil. (Kieffer 1912). *Telenomus seychellensis* Kieffer, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kieffer 1912).

Family SPHEGIDAE *Crabro oceanicus* Turner, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Turner 1911). *C. scotti* Turner, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Turner 1911). *Notogonia reticulata* Saussier - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Turner 1911). *N. seychellensis* Cameron, 1907 - End.; M. & Sil. (Turner 1911). *Pison isolatum* Turner, 1911 - End.; M. & Sil. (Turner 1911). *Scellphron hemipterum* (Fabricius) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Turner 1911) & P. *Tachysphex micromegas* Saussier, ... - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Turner 1911)

Family VESPIDAE *Polistes olivaceus* (De Geer, 1773) - Indo-Pacific; M., Moy., Sil. (Meade Waldo 1912), P., A. & LD.

COLEOPTERA

Family ANOBIIDAE *Caenocara subplana* Scott, 1924 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1924) & P. *Dorcatoma insulana* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *Mesothetes tenuibrachium* Scott, 1924 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1924). *Mesocoelopsis silhouettae* Scott, 1924 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1924). *Metadorcatoma peculiaris* Scott, 1924 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1924). *Metatheca rugulosa* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *Mirosternus excisipalpis* Scott, 1924 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1924) & P. *Nesothecha cognata* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *N. communis* Scott, 1924 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1924) & P. *N. germana* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *N. lateoblonga* Scott, 1924 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1924) & P. *N. maxima* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *N. sinuillima* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *N. typica* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924).

Family ANTHRIBIDAE *Acharagus tener* Jordan, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Jordan 1914). *Araecerus fasciculatus* (Degeer, 1775) - Pantrop.; M., Long, Sil. (Jordan 1914) & P. *Choragus bolus* Jordan, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Jordan 1914). *Cleranthribus colydiopsis* Jordan, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Jordan 1914). *Corynnocia scotti* Jordan, 1914 - End. gen.; Sil. (Jordan 1914). *Dysnos aethiops* Jordan, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Jordan 1914). *Epitaphius licheneus* Jordan, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Jordan 1914). *Hormiscops luetus* Jordan, 1914 -

- End.; Sil. (Jordan 1914) & P. *H. sorbrinus* Jordan, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Jordan 1913) *H. tibialis* Jordan, 1914 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Jordan 1914) & P. *Scirtetinus eumelas* Jordan, 1914 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Jordan 1914), P. & Fel. *S. piceus* Jordan, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Jordan 1914) & P. *Sintorops allaeus* Jordan, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Jordan 1914).
- Family BOSTRYCHIDAE *Xylothrips flavipes* Illiger - Indo-Pacific; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921).
Xylopsocus capucinus Fabricius - Pantropical; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921).
- Family BRENTHIDAE *Euphasalis amitina* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924).
- Family BUPRESTIDAE *Iridotaenia mahena* Fairmaire, 1891 - End.; M. & Sil. (Matyot 1996a)
- Family CARABIDAE *Tetragonoderus bilunatus* Klug, 1832 - Mad., M., Sil. (Scott 1912), P. & Bird.
- Family CERAMBYCIDAE *Ceresium flavipes* Fabricius - Masc.; M. & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922)
Coptops humerosa Fairmaire - End.; M. & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *Mahenes semifasciata* Aurvillus, 1922 - End. gen.; M., Long & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *Microndemia albosenata* Aurvillus, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *M. glauca* Aurvillus, 1922 - End.; Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *Obrium nitidicolle* Aurvillus, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *Olenecamptus bilobus* Fabricius - Masc.; M. & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *Pterolophia instabilis* Aurvillus, 1922 - End.; M., Long, Anon. & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922). *Sybra geminata* Klug - Afr.; M., SA, & Sil. (Aurvillus 1922).
- Family CHRYSOMELIDAE *Bikasha fortipunctata* Maulik, 1929 - End.; M., Sil. (Maulik 1929) & P. *B. tenuipunctata* Maulik, 1929 - Ald.; M. & Sil. (Maulik 1929). *Chaetocnema krishna* Maulik, 1929 - End.; M., Sil. (Maulik 1929) & P. *C. mahensis* Maulik, 1929 - End.; M. & Sil. (Maulik 1929). *Diacantha unifasciata* (Olivier) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Maulik 1929). *Eka nigra* Maulik, 1929 - End. gen.; Sil. (Maulik 1929). *Pratinia costata* Maulik, 1929 - End. gen.; Sil. (Maulik 1929). *P. variabilis* Maulik, 1929 - End.; M. & Sil. (Maulik 1929). *Rhyparida scotti* Maulik, 1929 - End.; M. & Sil. (Maulik 1929).
- Family CHIDAE *Cis bicinctus* Reitter, 1908 - Mad.; M., Sil. (Scott 1926) & P. *C. cacuminum* Scott, 1926 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *C. parallelus* Scott, 1926 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *C. retithorax* Scott, 1926 - End.; M., Long, Sil. (Scott 1926) & Fel. *C. silvicola* Scott, 1926 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *C. sublacernatus* Scott, 1926 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1926), P. & LD. *C. subsquamosus* Scott, 1926 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *Dimeropterocis apterus* Scott, 1926 - End. gen.; Sil. (Scott 1926). *Ennearthron cucullatum* Melle, 1848 - Afr.; M., Sil. (Scott 1926) & Fel. *E. pulchellum* Scott, 1926 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1926) & P. *Paratrichapus sechellarum* Scott, 1926 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *Tropicis brevicarinatus* Scott, 1926 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *T. flexicarinatus* Scott, 1926 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926). *Xylogaphus sechellensis* Scott, 1926 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1926).
- Family CISTELIDAE *Mycteromimus insularis* Champion, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914).
- Family CLERIDAE *Anthriboclerus scotti* Schenkling, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Schenkling 1921).
Pallens laterisignatus Schenkling, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Schenkling 1921). *Stecyldrus dimidiatus* Schenkling, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Schenkling 1921).
- Family COCCINELLIDAE *Nephus sechellensis* Sicard, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Sicard 1913).
Phlyctenolotis scotti Sicard, 1913 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Sicard 1913). *Pallus arrowi* Sicard, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Sicard 1913). *P. phytonus* Mulsant - Mad.; M., Sil. (Sicard 1913) & Mar. *Rhodolia chermesina* Mulsant - Mad., M., Long, Sil. (Sicard 1913) & Denis. *R. dlonyia* (Sicard, 1909) - Mad.; M., Long, Sil. (Sicard 1913) & Denis. *Scymnus constrictus* Mulsant - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Sicard 1913), Fel. & Bird. *S. cryptogonoides* Sicard, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Sicard 1913). *S. grunerne* (Sicard, 1909) - Mad.; M., Long, Anon., Sil. (Sicard 1913) & Bird. *S. intercisus* (Sicard, 1909) - End.; M., Anon. & Sil. (Sicard 1913). *S. lunulatus* (Sicard, 1912) - Masc.; Sil. (Sicard 1913); *S. oblongosignatus* (Muls.) - Indian Ocean; M., Long, Anon. & Sil. (Sicard 1913). *Sticholotis madagassa* Weise, 1909 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Floater 1991). *Xamerpillus guhani* Sicard, 1912 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Sicard 1913).
- Family COLYDIIDAE *Axiocerylon cavicolle* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1918).
Cerylon curvulum Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *C. gardineri* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *C. longuis* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1918) & P. *C. perparvulum* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1918) &

P. Cicones scotti Grouvelle, 1918 - End; Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *Ditoma cavicollis* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *Lascotonus scotti* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *Mychocerus alluaudi* Grouvelle, 1894 - End.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). P. & LD. *Neotrichus gardineri* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *Pycnometus confertus* (Reitter, 1878) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1918) & P. *Sarothrius eximius* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *Thyroderus scuticollis* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *Xuthia sicana* Pascoe, 1863 - Afr.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1918) & Fel.

Family CORYLOPHIDAE *Daubania seychellarum* Scott, 1917 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Scott 1917) & P. *Lewisium seychellaeum* Scott, 1917 - End.; M., Long, Sil. (Scott 1917), P. & Fel. *Meioderus quinnyanus* Scott, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1917). *Orthoperus minutissimus* Matthews, 1899 - Introduced?; Sil. (Scott 1917). *Sacium grossianum* Scott, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1917). *S. picaultianum* Scott, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1917). *S. rochonianum* Scott, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1917). *S. roslanionum* Scott, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1917). *Sericoderus seychellensis* Scott, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1917).

Family CRYPTOPHAGIDAE *Hapalips scotti* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914).

Family CUCUJIDAE *Laemophloeus propior* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *Inopeplus mimetes* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *Monanus concinnulus* (Walker, 1858) - Cosmo.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *M. ornatus* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *Oryzaephilus sarinamensis* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Cosmo.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *Prostomina convexuscula* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *Psammoeus laetulus* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *P. nitescens* Grouvelle, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *P. simoni* Grouvelle, 1892 - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *Silvanus scuticollis* Walker, 1859 - Cosmo.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1914). *S. hebetatus* Grouvelle, 1912 - Afr.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1914).

Family CURCULIONIDAE *Acalles seychellensis* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Baridomorpha triplaris* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Calandra stigmaticollis* (Gyll.) - Indo-Pacific; M., Anon. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Choerorhinos tenuiculus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Cossonatus suturalis* Boheman - Afr.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Cratopus griseovestitus* Linell, 1897 - End.; M., Long, Anon., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *C. muticus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Floater 1991 as 'curculionid beetle'). *C. segregatus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *Cryptorhynchidius graniger* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *Cycloterinus ampliatus* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; Sil. (Kolbe 1910; Champion 1914). *C. humeralatus* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *C. microphthalmus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *C. sechellarum* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *C. sphaeropterus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Endaeopsis anthonomoides* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *E. curvianus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *E. delicatus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Eucylopterus terreus* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *Eugnoristus braueri* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Eucops viriditinctus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Himatium brevisculum* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *H. rugipenne* Champion, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *Lasiotrupis clavigera* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Lepydus nepenthicola* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Microtrupis longipennis* Chapman, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *M. piligera* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *M. puncticeps* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Orthotennus filiformis* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Phloeophagosoma conicicollis* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Phoenicobates alatus* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. alboscotus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. curvipes* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. cylindricus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. duplovestitus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. flexirostris* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. foveiventris* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. gibbirostris* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion

1914) *P. hispidulus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. nigrolimbatus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *P. pandanicola* Champion, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *P. peropaeus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. simplex* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. stevensonlae* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *P. stricticollis* Champion, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *P. tenuis* Champion, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *P. vittatus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Phoenicobatopsis echinatus* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Polytus mellerborgi* (Boheman) - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *Proeces compressicollis* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Rhetogenes sexeristatus* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; Long & Sil. (Champion 1914). *R. spurcus* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Rhombosoma acuminatum* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Rhynchaenus spissus* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Rhyncotosoma dubium* (Gahan, 1900) - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & Fel. *Sphodrius magdalooides* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Stenopentarthrum pandanae* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Stenouimius orientalis* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Stenotrupis bififormis* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. caliginosa* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. coniccephala* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. convexiuscula* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. dumetorum* Chapman, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *S. filum* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. nemoralis* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. parallela* Champion, 1914 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914) & P. *S. polita* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. sericata* Champion, 1914 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *S. silvicola* Champion, 1914 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1914). *Trapezirrhynchus silhouettensis* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; Sil. (Champion 1914). *Tragionorrhampus tuberculirostris* Champion, 1914 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Champion 1914), P., Fel. & Mar.

Family DERMESTIDAE *Attagenus undulatus* (Motschulsky, 1858) - Pantrop.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *Orphinus brevicornis* (Sharp, 1885) - Pantrop.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *Paratrogoderma mahense* Scott, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924).

Family DYTISCHIDAE *Copelatus gardineri* Scott, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1912) & P. *C. pandanorum* Scott, 1912 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1912) & P.

Family ELATERIDAE *Alaus scotti* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923). *Cardiphorus lutosus* Candèze, 1896 - Comoros; M., Long, Anon., Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923), P. & Denis. *Conoderus dimidiaticollis* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923). *C. gracilipes* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923). *Dactylosinus dorsalis* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; M. & Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923). *Gonodyrus tarsalis* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923). *Melanoxanthus frivulus* Candèze, 1900 - Asia; M., Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923) & P. *M. insularis* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923). *Porthmidius solitarius* Fleutiaux, 1923 - End.; Sil. (Fleutiaux 1923).

Family ENDOMYCHIDAE *Anagaricophilus pulchellus* Arrow, 1922 - End.; M. & Sil. (Arrow 1922). *Cirtomychus coccinelloides* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; M., Sil. (Arrow 1922) & P. *C. minor* Arrow, 1922 - End.; M., Sil. (Arrow 1922) & P.

Family EROTYLIDAE *Euxestus globosus* Arrow, 1922 - End.; Sil. (Arrow 1922).

Family HELODIDAE *Cyphon insularis* Champion, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1924). *Ptilodactyla scabrosa* Champion, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1924). *Scirtes seychellensis* Champion, 1924 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1924).

Family HISTERIDAE *Acritus daubani* Scott, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1913). *A. davidsoni* Scott, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1913). *Bacanius ambiguus* Schmidt, 1893 - End.; Long, Sil. (Scott 1913), P., Fel. & L.J. *Platysoma tenuimargo* Schmidt, 1893 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1913) & L.J. *Paromatus alluandi* Schmidt, 1893 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1913) & L.J. *P. calciger* Scott, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1913).

Family HYDROPHILIDAE *Bourdonnaisia silhouettae* Scott, 1913 - End. gen.; Sil. (Scott 1913). *Cereyon fruticola* Scott, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1913) & P. *C. laicollis* Regimbart, 1903 - Mad.; Long, Sil. (Scott 1913) & P. *C. uniformis* Sharp, 1890 - Introduced?; M. &

- Sil. (Scott 1913) *Dactylosternum insulare* (Castelnau, 1840) - Cosmo.; M., Sil. (Scott 1913) & P. *Philydrus abnormalis* Sharp, 1890 - Palaeotrop.; Sil. (Scott 1913). *Paromicrus atomus* Scott, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1913), P. & Fel. *P. carinatus* Scott, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1913) & P. *P. thomasseti* Scott, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1913) & P.
- Family LATHRIDIIDAE *Ericinus minutus* (Linnaeus) - Cosmo.; Sil. (Scott 1921). *Metophthalmus alhofasciatus* Reitter, 1891 - Cosmo.; Sil. (Scott 1921). *Nesolathrus typicus* Scott, 1921 - End. gen., M., Sil. (Scott 1921) & P. *Ostomopsis solitaria* Scott, 1921 - End. gen.; Sil. (Scott 1921).
- Family LUCANIDAE *Figulus seychellensis* Scott, 1912 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1912). *F. striatus* (Oliver, 1789) - Mad.; M., Sil. (Scott 1912) & P.
- Family LYMEXYLONIDAE *Melittoma insulare* Fairmaire, 1893 - Mad.; M., Sil. (Scott 1924) & P.
- Family MELASIDAE *Fornax sternalis* Bonvouloir, 1872 - Asia; Sil. (Fleuryaux 1923).
- Family MELYRIDAE *Xamerpus cioides* Champion, 1924 - Asa; Sil. (Champion 1924).
- Family MORDELLIDAE *Gilpa tricholor* Wiedl - Asia; Sil. (Champion 1917). *Mordella coleae* Champion, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1917). *M. disparilis* Champion, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1917). *Mordellistena argutula* Champion, 1917 - End.; M., Ro., Anon., Sil. (Champion 1917) & Fel. *M. dirempta* Champion, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1917) & P. *M. degressa* Champion, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1917). *M. partilis* Champion, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1917). *M. septemcarinata* Champion, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1917) & P.
- Family MYCETOPHAGIDAE *Propalticus sechellarum* Scott, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921).
- Family NITIDULIDAE *Brachypeplus aequalis* (Walker, 1858) - Asia; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913), P. & Mar. *B. notatus* Murray, 1864 - Asia; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913), P., Mar. & LD. *Carpophilus angustatus* Murray, 1864 - Mad.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *C. dimidiatus* (Fabricius, 1792) - Afr., M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913) & P. *C. fusciceps* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *C. hemipterus* (Linnaeus, 1767) - Cosmo.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *C. humeralis* (Fabricius, 1798) - Palaeotrop.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913), P. & Fel. *C. scotti* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *Cillaeus megacephalus* Castelnau, 1835 - Mad.; Long & Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *C. micros* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *C. opaculus* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *Cybocephalus brevis* Grouvelle, 1913 - Ami.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *C. minutus* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; M., Anon., Sil. & P. *C. tantilus* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913) & P. *Haptoncus luteolus* (Erichson) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). P. & Mar. *H. minutus* (Reitter, 1873) - Palaeotrop.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *H. ocularis* (Fairmaire, 1849) - Pantrop.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1913), P. & LD. *Pria nitidior* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1913). *Stelidota explanata* Grouvelle, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1913).
- Family NOTIOPHYGIDAE *Aphanocephalus acuminatus* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M. & Sil. (Grouvelle 1918). *A. insularis* Grouvelle, 1918 - End.; M., Sil. (Grouvelle 1918) & P.
- Family OEDEMERIDAE *Ananea scabripennis* Champion, 1917 - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Champion 1917) & P. *Oxacis griseescens* (Fairmaire, 1897) - Masc.?, M., Sil. (Champion 1917), P., Fel & Bird.
- Family OSTOMIDAE *Lophocateres pusillus* (Klug, 1832) - Cosmo.; Sil. (Grouvelle 1918).
- Family PIJILIDAE *Eurygenius convexicollis* Champion, 1917 - End.; Sil. (Champion 1917).
- Family PLATYPODIDAE *Platypus lepidus* Chapuis, 1866 - Asia; Sil. (Sampson 1914) & P.
- Family PHALACRIDAE *Nesiotus similis* Scott, 1921 - End. gen., M., Anon. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *N. tropicus* Scott, 1921 - End.; M., Long, Ro., Sil. (Scott 1921) & P. *Parisechus seychellensis* Scott, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Scott 1921) & P. *Phalacrotomus exiguus* Scott, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *Stilboides angulicaps* Scott, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1921).
- Family PSELAPHIDAE *Batrissodes caudatus* Raffray, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Raffray 1913) & P. *Batraxis egregia* Raffray, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Raffray 1913) & P. *Hughia carinata* Raffray, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Raffray 1913). *Thesiastes cordicollis* Raffray, 1882 - Afr.; M., Long, Sil. (Raffray 1913) & P. *Sunorfoides bicolor* Raffray, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Raffray 1913). *S. picea* Raffray, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Raffray 1913). *S. punctipennis* Raffray, 1913 - End.; M. & Sil. (Raffray 1913). *Triomicrus seychellensis* Raffray, 1913 - End.; Sil. (Raffray 1913).

- Family PTILIIDAE (=TRICHOPTERYGIDAE) *Acrotrichis ovatula* Motschulsky, 1808 - End., M. & Sil (Britten 1926). *Ptiliodes pruinosis* Britten, 1926 - End., Sil. (Britten 1926). *Ptiliolum rufotestaceum* (Matthews, 1894) - Caribbean; Sil. (Britten 1926). *Pinella impressicollis* Britten, 1926 - End., M. & Sil. (Britten 1926). *Throscidium brunneum* Britten, 1926 - End., M. & Sil. (Britten 1926).
- Family PTINIDAE *Ptinus monticola* Scott, 1924 - End., M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *P. sechellarum* Scott, 1924 - End., M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *Sulcoptinus gothicus* (Scott, 1924) - End., M. & Sil. (Scott 1924).
- Family RHIPICERIDAE *Callirhipis philiberti* Fairmaire, 1891 - End., M., Long, Sil. (Scott 1926), P. & LD.
- Family SCARABAEIDAE *Aphodius nigritus* Fabricius, 1801 - Afr.; M., Long, Sil. (Scott 1912), Fel. & LD. *Adoretus versutus* Harold, 1869 - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Scott 1912) & P. *Nesohoplia senecionis* Scott, 1912 - End., gen., M. & Sil. (Scott 1912). *Oryctes monoceros* (Olivier, 1789) - Afr.; M., Sil. (Scott 1912), P., Freg. & Denis. *Oxyomus palmarum* Scott, 1912 - End., M. & Sil. (Scott 1912). *Saprosites lateiceps* (Fairmaire, 1871) - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Scott 1912).
- Family SCOLYTIDAE *Coccotrypes declivis* Sampson, 1914 - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Sampson 1914). *C. furvus* (Sampson, 1914) Sampson, 1914 - End.; M. Sil. (Sampson 1913). *C. sp.* - ?; Sil. (Sampson 1914). *Cryphalus pallidus* Eichhoff, 1871 - Afr., M. & Sil. (Sampson 1914). *C. trypanus* Sampson, 1913 - End., M., Sil. (Sampson 1914) & Mar. *Eccoctopterus spinosus* (Olivier) - Palaeotrop.; M. & Sil. (Sampson 1914 as *E. sexspinus*). *Hypothenemus birmanus* Eichhoff, 1879 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Sampson 1914). *Hypothenemus eruditus* Westwood, 1836 - Cosmo.; M., Long, Sil. (Sampson 1914) & P. *Xyleborinus andrewesi* (Blandford, 1896) - Asia; Sil. (Sampson 1914). *X. crassusculus* (Motschulsky) Blandford, 1896 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Sampson 1914 as *X. semigranosus*). *Xyleborus ferrugineus* (Fabricius) - Pantrop.; M., Long, Sil. (Sampson 1914 as *X. confusus*) & P. *X. piceus* (Motschulsky) Schaaf, 1891 - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Sampson 1914 as *X. madagascariensis*). *X. perforans* (Wollaston, 1857) - Asia; M., Anon., Sil. (Sampson 1914), P. & LD. *X. volvatus* (F.) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Sampson 1914 as *X. torquatus*) & LD.
- Family SCYDMAENIDAE *Eucouanus senex* Scott, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *Nesenthla cordithorax* Scott, 1921 - End., gen.; Sil. (Scott 1921). *N. minor* Scott, 1921 - End., M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *N. polita* Scott, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Scott 1921). *N. typica* Scott, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *Nesotoxidium typicum* Scott, 1921 - End., gen.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *Scaphosoma achedranum* Scott, 1921 - End., M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *S. pictum* Motschulsky, 1863 - Asia; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *S. silhouettae* Scott, 1921 - End., Sil. (Scott 1921). *Seydmanus armatus* Scott, 1921 - Indian Ocean; M., Long, Sil. (Scott 1921) & Fel. *S. insularum* Scott, 1921 - End., M., Sil. (Scott 1921) & P. *S. seychellensis* Scott, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921). *Toxidium seychellense* Scott, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Scott 1921).
- Family SPHINDIDAE *Aspidiphorus 'lareynii'* - ?; M. & Sil. (Scott 1924). *A. perexiguus* Scott, 1924 - End., M., Sil. (Scott 1924) & P.
- Family STAPHYLINIDAE *Alanygnathus piceus* Motschulsky - Asia; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & LD. *Anebolura minutissima* Bernhauer, 1921 - End., gen.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & Fel. *Astenus melanarius* Kust - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *A. scotti* Bernhauer, 1921 - End., M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Atheta coriaria* Motsch. - End., M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & Mar. *A. dilalipennis* Motsch. - Afr.-Asia; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921), P. & Mar. *A. insularis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *A. laeticollis* Fauvel - End., M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *Calaminus pennifer* Fauvel - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Coenonica puncticollis* Kraatz - Pantrop.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Conosoma alluaudi* (Fauvel) - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921), P. & LD. *C. heterocerus* (Fauvel) - Asia; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & LD. *C. rufiventre* (Fauvel) - Fnd.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921), P. & LD. *Coproporus atomus* Kraatz - Asia - M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *C. minimus* (Motschulsky) - Asia; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *C. tachyporoides* Kraatz - Afr.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Diachus punctipennis* Motsch. - Asia; M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Edaphus Afr. nus* Fpp. - Afr.; M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *E. sechellarum* Bernhauer, 1921 - End., M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *E. spectabilis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer

1921) & P. *Eleusis kraatzi* Fauvel, 1878 - Asia; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Espeon scotti* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Gyrophacna plicata* Fauvel - Mad.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *Leptacinus magniceps* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Leptusa longicollis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *L. tropica* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *Lispinus impressicollis* Motsch - Afr.-Asia; M., Long & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *L. obscurellus* Fauvel, 1904 - Mad.; M., Long & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *L. politulus* Fauvel, 1898 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). & LD. *L. specularis* Bernhauer, 1904 - Asia; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). & P. *Placusa insularis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Medon cephalotes* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *M. debilicorais* Wollaston - End.; M., Long, Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *M. duplicatus* Fauvel - Mad; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *M. nigripennis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *M. testaceomarginatus* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *M. trapeziformis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *M. varipennis* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Osorius sechellarum* Kolbe - End.; M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Paracyphea asperata* Bernhauer, 1921 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & P. *P. mahana* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). & Mar. *P. tenuipunctata* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Philonthus bisignatus* Boheman - Afr.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *P. fimbriolatus* Er. - Afr.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Phloconomus singularis* Kraatz, 1859 - End.; Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Stenus silvicola* Bernhauer, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Bernhauer 1921). *Thoracophorus alluaudi* Fauvel, 1878 - End.; M., Sil. (Bernhauer 1921) & LD.

Family TENEBRIONIDAE *Aphitobius crenatus* Klug, 1833 - Indian Ocean; M., Long, Sil. (Gebien 1921), P., Bird & Denis. *Amarygmus seychellensis* Gebien, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Bradymerus hispidus* Gebien, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *B. seychellensis* Gebien, 1921 - End.; M., Sil. (Gebien 1921) & Fel. *Camarothelops braueri* Kolbe, 1910 - End. gen.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Cherostus speculifrons* Gebien, 1921 - End.; Long & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Cryphaeus capreolus* Fairmaire, 1869 - Comoros; M., Sil. (Gebien 1921) & P. *Enicmosoma punctum* Gebien, 1921 - End.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Eutochia pulla* Er. - Afr.; M., Sil. (Gebien 1921) & P. *Gnathelops chatanayi* Gebien, 1921 - End. gen.; Sil. (Gebien 1921) & P. *Gonocephalum micantipenne* Fairmaire, 1893 - Afr.; M., Cerf, Long, Sil. (Gebien, 1921), P., Bird & Denis. *G. simplex* Fabricius - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Gebien 1921), P., Frog, Bird & Denis. *Heterophyllus atomus* Gebien, 1921 - End.; Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Platydema inaequidens* (Fairmaire, 1880) - Mad.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Pseudhadrus braueri* Kolbe, 1910 - End. gen.; Sil. (Kolbe 1910; Gebien 1921). *P. seriatus* Kolbe, 1910 - End.; M. & Sil. (Kolbe 1910; Gebien 1921). *Tagalus cavifrons* (Fairmaire, 1893) - End.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Tribolium castaneum* Herbst. - Introduced; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921). *Uloma crenatostriata* Fairmaire, 1868 - End.; M. & Sil. (Gebien 1921).

Family XYLOPHILIDAE *Xylophilus clavicornis* Champion, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1917) & P. *X. sechellarum* Champion, 1917 - End.; M. & Sil. (Champion 1917). *X. torticornis* Champion, 1917 - End.; M., Sil. (Champion 1917) & P.

CHORDATA

PISCES

Family RIVULIDAE *Pachyplanchax playfairii* Günther - End.; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1993) & P.

Family CICLIDAE *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Peters, 1852) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1994a; Gerlach & Canning 1996), P. & LD.

Family GOBIIDAE *Periophthalmus sobrinus* - Indian Ocean; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1994a; Gerlach & Canning 1996), P. & LD. *Bathygobius laddi* - Indian Ocean; M. & Sil. (Gerlach & Canning 1996).

Family BLENNIDAE *Ophiocara porocephala* - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1994a; Gerlach & Canning 1996), P. & LD.

AMPHIBIA

Family CAECILIIDAE *Grandisona alternans* Stejneger, 1906 - End. gen.; M., Sil (Boulenger 1909 & 1911; Nussbaum 1984; OUSE 1990; Hedges *et al.* 1993), P., LD & Freg. *G. brevis* (Boulenger, 1911) - End.; M. & Sil (OUSE 1990). *G. larvata* Ahl., - End.; M., Sil (Nussbaum 1984; Hedges *et al.* 1993), P. & LD. *G. sechellensis* (Boulenger, 1911) - End.; M., Sil (Boulenger 1909 as *Cryptopsophis multispicatus* & 1911; Nussbaum 1984; Hedges *et al.* 1993) & P. *Hypogeophis rostratus* Cuvier, 1829 - End. gen. M., Sil (Boulenger 1909 & 1911; Nussbaum 1984; Hedges *et al.* 1993), P., LD & Freg. *Praslinia cooperi* Boulenger, 1909 - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Hedges *et al.* 1993) & P.

Family HYPEROLIIDAE *Tachycnemis sechellensis* (Dumeril & Bibron, 1836) - End. gen.; M., Sil. (Boulenger 1911; Nussbaum & Wu 1995), P. & LD.

Family RANIIDAE *Ptychadena mascariensis* (Dumeril & Bibron, 1836) - Afr., Mascarenes; M., Sil (Boulenger 1911, Nussbaum 1984; OUSE 1990), P., LD. & Freg.

Family SOGLOSSIDAE *Nesomanis thomasseti* Boulenger, 1909 End. gen.; M., Sil (Boulenger 1911; Nussbaum 1984; OUSE 1990 as *Tachycnemis sechellensis*). *Sooglossus gardineri* (Boulenger, 1911) End. gen.; M., Sil (Boulenger 1911; Nussbaum 1984; OUSE 1990). *S. sechellensis* Boettger, 1896 End., M., Sil (Boulenger 1911; Nussbaum 1984; OUSE 1990)

REPTILIA

CROCODILIA

Family CROCODILIDAE *Crocodylus porosus* Cuvier - Indo-Pacific; formerly widespread, extinct - Sil. (Oger 1771).

CHELONIA

Family TESTUDINIDAE *Dipsochelys* spp. - End.; formerly widespread - Sil. (Oger 1771 in Bour 1984).

Family PELOMEPUSIDAE *Pelustos* spp. - End.; formerly widespread - Sil (Honegger 1966)

Family CHELONIIDAE *Chelonia mydas* (Linnaeus, 1766) - Pantrop.; widespread - Sil (Frazier 1984). *Eretmochelys imbricata* (Linnaeus, 1766) - Pantrop.; widespread - Sil. (Frazier 1984; Mortimer 1986).

Family CHAMAELONIDAE *Chamaeleo tigris* Kuhl, 1820 - End.; M., Sil. (Boulenger 1911; Gardiner 1986; OUSE 1990) & P.

Family COLUBRIDAE *Boaedon geometricus* (Schlegel, 1837) - End.; M., Sil. (Boettger 1896; Boulenger 1911), P. & Freg. *Lycognathophis sechellensis* (Schlegel, 1837) - End.; M., Sil. (Boulenger 1909; Nussbaum 1984; OUSE 1990), P., Coue., A. & Freg.

Family GEKKONIDAE *Alluronyx sechellensis* (Dumeril & Bibron, 1836) - End.; M., SA., Anon., Con., Ther., Sil. (Boulenger 1909; OUSE 1990; Gerlach & Canning 1996), P., CS., Co., Coe., A., Mar., Fel., GS., LD. & Freg. *Gehyra mutilata* (Wiegmann, 1835) - Introduced; M., SA., Cerf., Anon., Isl., Ther., Sil. (Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990), N., P., Cur., CS., GS., Fel., LD., Freg. & Denis. *Phelsuma astriata* Tamiel, 1901 - End.; M., SA., Cerf., Moy., Long., Cach., Anon., Isl., Con., Ther., Sil. (Boulenger 1909 as *P. madagascariense*; Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990), P., Cur., CS., R., Co., Coe., A., Fel., Coco, GS., PS., Mar., LD. & F. *P. sundbergi* Rendahl, 1939 - End.; M., SA., Cerf., Ro., Moy., Long., Cach., Anon., Sou., Isl., Con., Ther., Sil. (Boulenger 1909 as *P. madagascariense*; Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990), N., P., Cur., CS., R., Fel., Coco, GS., PS., Mar., LD. & F. *Urocotyledon inexpectata* (Stein.) - End.; M., Sil. (Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990); P., Cur., Cou., A., Coco, GS., Fel., LD. & Freg.

Family SCINCIDAE *Janetaescincus braueri* (Boettger, 1896) - End. gen.; M., S. (Boulenger 1911; Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990) & Freg. *Mubuya sechellensis* (Dumeril & Bibron, 1836) - End.; M., SA., Long., Cerf., Ro., Moy., Cach., Anon., Pet., Isl., Con., Ther., Sil. (Boulenger 1909; Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990), N., P., Cur., CS., R., Co., Coe., A., Fel., Coco, GS., PS., Mar., LD., Freg., Bird. & Denis. *Pamelaescincus gardineri* (Boulenger, 1909) - End. gen.; M., Cerf., Sil. (Boulenger 1911; Gardner 1986; OUSE 1990), P., Cur., R., Cou., A., PS., GS., LD. & Freg.

AVES

- Family FREGATIDAE *Phaethon lepturus* Lacépède & Daudin, 1802 - Panthrop., M., Sil. (Newton 1867; Penny 1974; OUSE 1990), Co., Coe. & A
- Family LARIIDAE *Gygis alba* Sparrm, 1786 - Indo-Pacific; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1993), P., Co., Coe., A., LD. & Freg.
- Family ARDEIDAE *Butoroides striatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Panthrop., M., Sil. (OUSE 1990), P., Co., Coe., A., LD., & Freg.
- Family FALCONIDAE *Falco araea* Oberholser, 1904 - End.; M., Cerf. Sil. (Newton 1867; Watson 1981; Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Fel., Mar., & LD.
- Family RALLIDAE *Gallinula chloropus* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Cosmo.; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1993), P., Co., Coe., A., & LD.
- Family COLUMBIDAE *Columba livia* Gmelin, 1789 - Introduced; M., Sil. (Gerlach 1993) & P. *Streptopelia picturata* (Temminck) - Mad.; M., Sil. (Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Co., Coe., A., Mar., Fel. & Freg. *Geopelia striata* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., A., Cou., Coe., Mar., Fel., LD. & Freg. *Alectroenas pulcherrima* (Sonnerat, 1768) - End.; M., Sil. (Watson 1984; Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., A., Fel., Mar., LD. & Freg.
- Family PSITTACULIDAE *Agapornis cana* (Gmelin) - Introduced, extinct; M. & Sil. (Penny 1974). *Psittacula eupatria* Linnaeus, 1758 - Asia, extinct; M., Sil. (Newton 1867; North 1892) & P.
- Family OTIDAE *Tyto alba* (Scopoli, 1769) - Introduced; M., Sil. (Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Co., Coe., A. & Freg.
- Family HYPSIPETIDAE *Hypsipetes crassirostris* Newton, 1867 - Com.; M., Sil. (Newton 1867; Watson 1984; Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Mar., Fel. & LD.
- Family NECTARIDAE *Nectarinia dussumieri* (Hartlaub, 1860) - End.; M., Sil. (Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Co., Coe., A., Mar., Fel., LD. & Freg.
- Family PLOCEIDAE *Foudla madagascariensis* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Mad.; M., Cerf. Sil. (Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Co., Coe., A., Mar., Fel., LD. & Freg.
- Family STURNIDAE *Aeridotheres tristis* (Linnaeus, 1766) - Introduced; widespread, M., Sil. (Greig-Smith 1989; OUSE 1990), P., Co., Coe., A., Mar., Fel., LD. & Freg.

MAMMALIA

- Family CERVIDAE *Cervus timorensis* - Introduced, extinct; Sil. (Racey & Nicoll 1984) & Freg.

CHIROPTERA

- Family EMBALLONURIDAE *Coleura seychellensis* Peters, 1896 - End.; M., Sil. (Wright 1868, Thomas 1915; Nicoll & Suttie 1982; Matyot 1996c), P. & LD.
- Family PTEROPIDAE *Pteropus seychellensis* Milne Edwards, 1887 - Com., Ald.; M., Sil. (Wright 1868; OUSE 1990), P. & LD.

RODENTIA

- Family MURIDAE *Rattus rattus* (Linnaeus, 1758) - Introduced, M, SA, Cerf, Long, Sil. (Scott 192; OUSE 1990), N., P., Cur., Fel., Mar., LD & Freg.

References

- Adams, H. 1868 - Description of some new species of shells collected by Geoffrey Nevill Esq., at Mauritius, the Isle of Bourbon and the Seychelles. *Proc. Zool. Soc. Lond.* (1868): 288-292.
- Agnall, R.S. 1921 - On Thysanoptera from the Seychelles Islands and Rodriguez. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9 7, 257-293.
- Arrow, G.J. 1922 - Coleoptera, Erotylidae and Endomychidae from the Seychelles, Chagos and Amirantes Islands. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9 10, 73-83.
- Attems, C.G. 1900 - Dr. Bruer's Myriopoden-Ausbeute auf den Seychellen im Jahre 1895. *Zool. Jahrb. (Syst.)* 13: 133-171.

- Aurivillius, C. 1922 - Coleoptera (Cerambycidae) from the Seychelles islands, Aldabra and Rodriguez. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9 10, 421-443.
- Austen, E.E. 1920 - The Percy Sladen Trust Expedition to the Indian Ocean in 1905 and in 1907-1909, under Mr J. Stanley Gardiner, M.A. Diptera: Tabanidae. *Bull. ent. Res.* 11, 43-45.
- Bagnall, R.S. 1921 - Thysanoptera. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9 7, 257-293.
- Benoit, P.L.G. 1978 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Seychelles. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 92 (2); 405-420, 663-674, 675-679, 680-689, 690-699, 899-901, 940-946.
- 1979a - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Seychelles. Oonopidae (Araneae). *Rev. Zool. afr.* 93 (1); 185-222.
- 1979b - Amblypygi et Scorpiones. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 93; 458-460.
- Bernhauer, M. 1922 - Coleoptera, Staphylinidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 18, 165-186.
- Bezzi, M. 1923 - Diptera, Bombyliidae and Myiodaria (Coenosiniinae, Muscinae, Calliphorinae, Sarcophaginae, Dexiinae, Tachininae), from the Seychelles and neighbouring islands. *Parasitology* 15, 75-102.
- Boettger, O. 1896 - Neue Kriechtiere (*Scalotes*, *Arthrolepis*) von den Seychellen. *Zool. Anz.* 19, 349-351.
- Bolivar, I. 1912 - Orthoptera: Acrydiidae, Phasgonuridae, Gryllidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 263-292.
- 1924 - Orthoptera: Dictyoptera (Blattidae and Mantidae), and a supplement to Gryllidae, of the Seychelles and adjacent islands. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9 13, 313-359.
- Bolivar, I. & Ferriere, C. 1912 - Orthoptera, Phasmidae of the Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 293-300.
- Borradaile, I.A. 1907 - Land and freshwater Decapoda. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond. (Zool.)* 12, 63-68.
- Boulenger, G.A. 1909 - A list of the freshwater fishes, batrachians and reptiles obtained by Mr J. Stanley Gardiner's expedition to the Indian Ocean. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 12, 291-300.
- 1911 - List of Batrachians, and Reptiles obtained by Prof. Stanley Gardiner on his second expedition to the Seychelles and Aldabra. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 14, 375-378.
- Bour, R. 1984 - Taxonomy, history and geography of Seychelles land Tortoises and fresh-water Turtles. In: *Biogeography and Ecology of the Seychelles Islands*. Monographiae Biologicae Vol. 55. (Ed: Stoddart, DR) Dr. W. Junk, The Hague, 281-308.
- Bonvier, E.L. 1913 - Les Caridines des Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond. (Zool.)* 15; 447-472.
- Brignoli, P.M. 1978 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Seychelles. Araneae Tetrablemmidae. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 92(2); 431-435.
- 1980 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Seychelles. Araneae Telemidae et Ochyroceratidae. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 94(2); 380-386.
- Brindle, A. 1976 - Dermapter of the Seychelles. *Rev. Zool. Bot. afr.* 90; 2
- Brown, D.S. & Gerlach, J. 1991 - On *Paludomus* and *Cleopatra* (Thiaridae) in Africa and the Seychelles islands. *J. Moll. Stud.* 57, 471-479.
- Budde-Lund, G. 1913 - Terrestrial Isopoda, particularly considering in relation to the distribution of the southern Indo-Pacific species. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 367-394.
- Britten, H. 1926 - Ptiliidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 19, 87-89.
- Burr, M. 1910 - Dermaptera. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond. (Zool.)* 14; 123-333
- Cameron, P. 1907 - Hymenoptera. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 (Zool.) 12, 69-86
- Campion, H. 1913 - Odonata. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 435-446.

- Carlström, A., Dogley, D., Fleisher-Dogley, F., Nolin, R. & Vernier, N. 1996 - *Silhouette Plant Conservation Expedition - 26-30 Jan 1996 - Report*, Division of Environment, Seychelles, Unpublished.
- Carpenter, G.H. 1916 - The Apterygota of the Seychelles. *Proc. R. Ir. Acad.*, B 33, 1-70.
- Champion, G.C. 1914 - Coleoptera, Curculionidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 393-497
- ". 1917 - Coleoptera, Heteromera (excluding Tenebrionidae) from the Seychelles Islands and Aldabra. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 8 19, 161-187.
- ". 1924 - Coleoptera from the Seychelles: Lampyridae, Helodridae, Cantharidae, Melyridae, and supplement to Cleridae Islands and Aldabra. *Trans. R. ent. Soc., Lond.* (1924); 295-304.
- Christensen, C. 1912 - On the ferns of the Seychelles and the Aldabra group. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.* 2. (Bot.) 7; 409-425
- Cockerell, T.D.A. 1912 - Hymenoptera, Apoidea. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 29-41.
- Collin, J.E. 1912 - Diptera, Borboridae & Phoridae from Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 101-118.
- ". 1922 - Empididae from the Seychelles. *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 58, 184-189.
- Demange, J.-M. 1981 - Myriapoda - Chilopoda. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 95: 623-652.
- Distant, W.L. 1909 - 'Sealark' Rhynchota. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 13, 29-48.
- ". 1913 - Rhynchota. Part I: Suborder Heteroptera. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 139-191.
- Eaton, A.E. 1913 - Diptera, Psychodidae & Ephemerae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 423-434.
- Edwards, F.W. 1912 - Diptera, Tipulidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 195-214.
- Enderlein, G. 1910 - Embiidina und Neuroptera (Coniopterygidae und Hemerobiidae). Diptera, Mycetophilidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 14, 55-81.
- ". 1912 - Diptera, Sciaridae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 181-194.
- ". 1931 - Die Copeognathen-fauna der Seychellen. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 19, 207-240.
- Gebien, H. 1922 - Coleoptera, Heteromera: Tenebrionidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 18, 261-324.
- Grasshoff, 1980 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Séchelles. Araneidae-Arghiopidae, Araneidae-Araneinae (Araneae). *Rev. Zool. afr.* 94(2), 387-409.
- Enderlein, G. 1913 - Diptera: Scatopsidae, Simuliidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 373-375.
- Esben-Petersen, P. 1927 - Neuroptera: Chrysopidae of Seychelles and adjacent islands. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9 19, 445-455.
- Ferrara, F. & Taiti, S. 1983 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Séchelles (Mission P.L.G. Benoit - J.J. Van Mol 1972). Isopodi terrestri. *Annl. Mus. v. Afr. cent.*, 8 (Zool.) 240, 1-94.
- Fletcher, T.B. 1910 - Lepidoptera, exclusive of the Tortricidae and Tineidae, with some remarks on their distribution and means of dispersal amongst the islands of the Indian Ocean. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 13, 265-324 & The Orneodidae and Pterophoridae of the Seychelles Expedition. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 13, 397-404.
- Floutiaux, F. 1923 - Coleoptera: Melasidae et Elateridae des Séchelles et des îles voisines. *Trans. R. ent. Soc., Lond.* (1923), 398-436.
- Floater, G.J. undated - *Studies on insect diversity in a tropical montane forest on Silhouette Island, Seychelles*. BA (Hons.) thesis, Univ. Oxford, Unpublished.
- ". 1993 - Lepidoptera on endemic plants of the Seychelles. *Ent. Rec.* 105, 255-256
- ". 1994 - Effects of habitat destruction on endemic Dermaptera of the Seychelles. *Ent. Mo. Mag.* 134; 59-61.
- ". 1995 - Seed predation and flower visiting by *Epicroesa* sp. (Lepidoptera: Heliodinidae) on a rare Seychelles tree. *Phelsuma* 3, 31-40.

- Forel, A. 1907 - Fourmis des Seychelles, Amirantes, Farquhar et Chagos. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 (Zool.) 12, 91-94.
- 1912 - Fourmis des Seychelles et des Aldabras, reçues de M. Hugh Scott. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 159-167.
- Frazier, J. 1984 - Marine turtles in the Seychelles and adjacent territories. In: *Biogeography and Ecology of the Seychelles Islands*. Monographiae Biologicae Vol. 55. (Ed. Stoddart, DR) Dr W. Junk, The Hague, 417-468.
- Fridemann, F. 1986a - *Flowers and trees of Seychelles*. Editions Delroisse, Paris. 196pp.
- 1987a (for 1986) - Revision des *Arialaceae* des Seychelles. *Adansonia* 3, 245-256.
- 1987b - Étude de la structure du périanthe chez des *Pisonia* paléotropicaux et description de *P. sechellarum* sp. nov. (*Nyctagynaceae*). *Adansonia* 4; 383-392.
- 1990 - Une espèce nouvelle de *Psychotria* (*Rubiaceae*) des Seychelles. *Adansonia* 1; 65-67.
- 1994 - *Flore des Seychelles. Dicotylédones*. ORSTOM, Paris. 663pp.
- Fryer, J.C. 1912 - The Lepidoptera of Seychelles and Aldabra, exclusive of the Ormeoidea and Pterophoridae and of the Tortricina and Tineina. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 1-28.
- Gardner, A.S. 1986 - The biogeography of the lizards of the Seychelles Islands. *J. Biogeog.* 13, 237-253.
- Gerlach, J. 1987 - *The Land Snails of Seychelles - a field guide*. Gerlach, Weedon. 43 pages.
- 1993 - The conservation of Silhouette island, Seychelles. II. Animals. *Phelsuma* 1, 30-38.
- 1994a - The management and conservation of the La Passe marsh, Silhouette. *Phelsuma* 2, 16-22.
- 1994b - Some new forms of plants from Seychelles. *Phelsuma* 2, 61-63.
- 1995 - New species of *Pachnodus* (Gastropoda: Enidae) from Seychelles. *J. Conch., Lond.* 35, 167-177.
- 1996a - The effects of habitat domination by invasive Melastomataceae. *Phelsuma* 4; 19-26.
- 1996b - The taxonomy and affinities of the genus *Priodiscus* (Mollusca; Gastropoda; Streptaxidae). *J. Conch., Lond.* 35, 357-368.
- Gerlach, J. & Canning, K.L. 1996 - *Seychelles Terrapin Conservation Project*. NPTS, unpublished.
- Gorochov, A.V. 1994 - To the knowledge of the Grylloidea (Orthoptera) of the Seychelles. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie* 73(1), 95-102.
- Green, E.E. 1907 - Notes on the Coccidae collected by the Percy Sladen Trust Expedition to the Indian Ocean; supplemented by a collection received from Mr. R. Dupont, Director of Agriculture, Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond., Zool.* 12, 197-207.
- Greig-Smith, P.W. 1989 - The distribution of native and introduced landbirds on Silhouette Island, Seychelles. *Biol. Conserv.* 38, 35-54.
- Grouvelle, A. 1913 - Coleoptera: Nitidulidae, Heteroceridae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 93-116.
- 1914 - Coleoptera: Cucujidae, Cryptophagidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 17, 141-159.
- 1918 - Coleoptera: Ostomidae, Monotomidae, Colydiidae and Notiophygidae from the Seychelles and Aldabra Islands. *Trans. Ent. Soc. Lond.* (1918), 1-57.
- Harding, W.A. 1913 - On a new land-lice from the Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 39-44.
- Hedges, S.B., Nussbaum, R.A. & Maxson, L.R. 1993 - Caeccilian phylogeny and biogeography inferred from mitochondrial DNA sequences of the 12S rRNA and 16S rRNA genes (Amphibia: Gymnophiona). *Herpetological Monographs* 7, 64-76.
- Helsdingen van, P.J. 1978 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Séchelles - Linyphiidae (Araneae). *Rev. Zool. afr.* 92(2); 889-898.
- Hirst, A.S. 1911 - The Araneae, Opiliones and Pseudoscorpiones. Percy Sladen Trust Expedition to the Indian Ocean in 1905 under the leadership of Mr. J. Stanley Gardiner. *Trans. Linn. Soc. London. Zool.* 14, 379-395.

- ". 1913 - Second report on the Arachnida - the Scorpions, Pedipalpi, and supplementary notes on the Opiliones and Pseudoscorpions. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 31-37.
- Honegger, R.E. 1966 - Beobachtungen an der Herpetofauna der Seychellen. *Salamandra* 2, 20-36.
- Jordan, K. 1914 - Coleoptera: Anthribidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 247-267.
- Kertész, K. 1912 - Diptera, Stratiomyidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 95-99.
- Kieffer, J.J. 1910 - Diagnoses de nouveaux genres et de nouvelles espèces de Scelionides (Hym.) des Iles Séchelles. *Bull. Soc. ent. Fr.* (1910), 292-294.
- ". 1911 - Hymenoptera; Cynipidae. Diptera; Cecidomyiidae, Chironomidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 14, 309-366.
- ". 1912 - Hymenoptera, Proctotrupeoidea. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 45-80.
- Kolbe, H.J. 1910 - Die Coleopterenfauna der Seychellen. *Mitt. Zool. Mus. Berl.* 5, 1-49.
- Kramer, K.U. 1992 - *Ferns collected in 1992 on the Islands of Mahe, Silhouette, Praslin, La Digue and Bird Island*. Unpublished.
- Lamb, C.G. 1914 - Diptera: Heteroneuridae, Ortalidae, Trypetidae, Sepsidae, Micropezidae, Drosophilidae, Geomyzidae, Milichidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 307-372.
- Legrand, H. 1965 - Lépidoptères des Iles Seychelles et d'Aldabra. *Mem. Mus. natn. Hist. nat., Paris, A* 37, 1-210.
- Laidlaw, F.F. 1907 - The Odonata. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 (Zool.) 12, 87-89.
- Lehtinen, P.T. 1996 - Revision of the Old World Holothyridae. *Invertebr. Taxon.* 9: 767-826
- Mahnert, V. 1978 - Die Pseudoskorpione (Arachnida) Kenyas. Familien Withiidae und Cheliferidae. *Tropical Zoology* 1(1), 39-89.
- Mahunka, S. 1984 - Terrestrial fauna of the granitic islands of the Seychelles Archipelago (Indian Ocean): Acari, Oribatida. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 98(3), 670-676.
- Malcomber, S. 1994 - *Nepenthes pervilletii*. Unpublished.
- Masi, L. 1917 - Chalcididae of the Seychelles Islands. *Novit. zool.* 24, 121-230.
- Matyot, P. 1990 - *Caraustus scotti* rediscovered. *Phasmid Study Group Newsletter* 44, 6-7.
- ". 1995 - The earwig "*Chaetospania gardineri*" (Burr, 1910) rediscovered. *Phelsuma* 3, 58-62.
- ". 1996a - The jewel beetles (Coleoptera: Buprestidae) of Seychelles. *Phelsuma* 4, 57-62.
- ". 1996b - New sites for some native plants of Seychelles. *Phelsuma* 4: 63-66
- ". 1996c - The sheath-tailed bat *Coleoura seychellensis* Peters, 1868 (Chiroptera: Emballonuridae) rediscovered on Silhouette island. *Phelsuma* 4: 67-68
- Maulik, S. 1913 - Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae: Hispininae of the Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 16, 237-242.
- ". 1917 - Cassidinae. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 8 19, 144-147.
- ". 1931 - Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae: Eumolpinae, Galerucinae and Halidinae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 19, 241-260.
- Maurics, J.-P. 1980 - Myriapoda - Diplopoda. *Rev. Zool. afr.* 94: 138-168
- Meade-Waldo, G. 1912 - Hymenoptera, Diptera. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 43-44.
- Meyrick, E. 1911 - Tortricina and Tineina. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 14, 263-307.
- Morley, C. 1912 - Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, 2 15, 169-179.
- Mortimer, J.A. 1986 - *Marine Turtles in the Republic of the Seychelles*. IUCN, Gland.
- Newton, E. 1867 - On the land birds of the Seychelles Archipelago. *Ibis* 3, 335-360
- Nicoll, M. & Suttie, J. 1982 - The sheath-tailed bat in the Seychelles islands. *J. Zool.* 197: 421-426
- NPTS 1996 - *Silhouette Conservation Management Plan*. NPTS unpublished.
- Nussbaum, R.A. 1984 - Amphibians of the Seychelles. In: *Biogeography and Ecology of the Seychelles Islands*. Monographiae Biologicae Vol. 55. (Ed. Stoddart, DR) Dr. W. Junk, The Hague, 379-416.

- Nussbaum, R.A & Sheng Hai Wu 1995 - Distribution, variation, and systematics of the Seychelles treefrog, *Tachycnemis seychellensis* (Amphibia: Anura: Hyperoliidae). *J. Zool., Lond* **236**, 383-406.
- Oger 1771 - Unpublished manuscript (Archives de France no. 44J186).
- Orban, S. 1995 - East Afr.n bryophytes, XV. Calymperaceae species collected in Seychelles Islands in 1993. *Fragm. Flor. Geobot.* **40**(1): 279-287
- OUSE 1990 - *Oxford University Silhouette Expedition - final report*. Unpublished.
- Penny, M. 1974 - *The birds of Seychelles*. Collins, London. 160 pages.
- Pocs, T. 1995 - East Afr.n bryophytes, XIV. Hepaticae from the Indian Ocean islands. *Fragm. Flor. Geobot.* **40**(1): 251-277
- Racey, P.A & Nicoll, M.E. 1984 - Mammals of the Seychelles. In: *Biogeography and Ecology of the Seychelles Islands*. Monographiae Biologicae Vol. 55. (Ed. Stoddart, DR) Dr. W. Junk, The Hague, 607-626.
- Ruffray, A. 1913 - Coleoptera: Pselaphidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 16**, 117-138.
- Rambila, M. 1984 - Opiliones. *Ann. Mus. R. Afr. Cent. Ser.* **8 242**, 1-86
- Roberts, M. 1978 - Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Séchelles. Theridiidae, Mysmenidae and gen. Theridiosoma. *Rev. Zool. afr.* **92**(4): 902-939.
- Robertson, S.A. 1989 - *Flowering Plants of Seychelles*. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. 327pp.
- Roth, L.M. 1996 - Cockroaches on the Seychelles Islands. *J. Afr. Zool.* **110**: 97-128.
- Saaristo, M.I. 1995 - Clubionids of the granitic islands of Seychelles (Aranea, Clubionidae). *Phelsuma* **3**: 53-57.
- 1996a - Theridiosomatid spiders of the granitic Seychelles (Araneae, Theridiosomatidae). *Phelsuma* **4**: 48-52.
- 1996b - Symphytognathidae (Arachnida, Araneae), a new spider family for the granitic islands of Seychelles. *Phelsuma* **4**: 53-56.
- Sampson, W. 1914 - Coleoptera: Platypodidae & Ipidae from the Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 16**, 379-391.
- Schenkling, S. 1922 - Coleoptera: Cleridae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 18**, 325-329.
- Scott, H. 1910 - Eight months' entomological collecting in the Seychelles, 1908-9. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 14**, 21-39.
- 1912 - Coleoptera, Lamellicornia and Adephaga. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 15**, 215-261.
- 1913 - Coleoptera: Hydrophilidae, Histeridae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 16**, 193-235.
- 1914 - Mallophaga, Aphaniptera, and Diptera Pupipara. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 17**, 161-167.
- 1917 - Corylophidae. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, **8 19**, 1-33.
- 1921 - Coleoptera: Scydmaenidae, Scaphidiidae, Phalacridae, Cucujidae (supplement), Lathridiidae, Mycetophagidae (including "Propallicus"), Bostrychidae, Lyctidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 18**, 195-260.
- 1924 - Coleoptera, Ciidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 19**, 1-41.
- 1926 - Carabidae, Rhipiceridae. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, **9 18**, 50-76.
- 1932 - Notes on insects associated with ants and termites in the Seychelles Islands. *Ent. Monthly Mag.* **68**, 169-172
- Sicard 1912 - Coleoptera, Coccinellidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2 15**, 361-366.
- Simon, E. 1893 - Mission scientifique de M. Ch. Alluaud aux îles Séchelles (Mars, Avri), Mai 1898). Araichnides. *Bull. Soc. Zool. France* **1893** (18): 204-211
- 1898 - Études arachnologiques. 29^e Mémoire. XLVI. Araichnides recueillis en par M. le Dr. A. Bruner (de l'Université de Marburg) aus Îles Séchelles. *Ann. Soc. Ent. France* **66**: 370-385
- Simroth, 1913. *Die Vaginuliden* p. 131-202
- Stein, P. 1910 - Diptera, Anthomyiidae, mit den gattungen *Rhinia* und *Idella*. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2, 14**

- Starmühlner, F. 1983 - Results of the Hydrobiological Mission 1974 of the Zoological Institute of the University of Vienna. *Ann. Naturhist. Mus. Wien* **84/B**, 127-249
- Summerhayes, V.S. 1931 - An enumeration of the angiosperms of the Seychelles archipelago. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2** 19, 261-299.
- Swabey, C. 1970 - The endemic flora of the Seychelles Islands and its conservation. *Bio. Cons.* **2**, 171-177.
- Sykes, E.R. 1909 - The land and freshwater mollusca of the Seychelles Archipelago. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, *Zool* **13**, 57-64.
- Theobald, F.V. 1912 - Diptera, Culicidae. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2** 15, 81-94.
- Thomas, O. 1915 - Notes on bats of the genus *Coleura*. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* (8) **15**; 576-579
- Thon, K. 1996 - Die aussere Morphologie und die Systematik der Holothyriden. *Zool. Jahrb. (Syst.)* **23**; 677-724
- Turner, R.E. 1911 - Fossorial Hymenoptera from the Seychelles and other islands in the Indian Ocean. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2** 14, 367-374.
- Ulmer, G. 1910 - Trichoptera. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2** 14, 41-54.
- Wanless, F.R. 1980 - A revision of the spider genera *Asamonea* and *Pandisus* (Araneae: Salticidae. *Bull. Br. Mus. nat. Hist. (Zool.)* **39**(4); 213-257.
- 1984 - Araneae - Salticidae. Contributions à l'étude de la faune terrestre des îles granitiques de l'archipel des Seychelles. *Mus. R. Afr. Cent., Tervuren, Belg. Ann. 8, Sci. Zool.* **241**; 1-84.
- Warburton, C. 1912 - The Acarina of the Seychelles. *Trans. Linn. Soc. Lond.*, **2** 15, 349-360.
- Watson, J. 1981 - *Population ecology, food and conservation of the Seychelles Kestrel (Falco araea) on Mahé*. Ph.D. Thesis, Aberdeen University.
- 1984 - Land birds: Endangered species of the granitic Seychelles. In: *Biogeography and Ecology of the Seychelles Islands*. Monographiae Biologicae Vol. 55. (Ed: Stoddart, DR) Dr. W. Junk, The Hague, 513-528.
- Wright, E.P. 1868 - Notes on the bats of the Seychelles group of islands. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* (4) **2**; 436-438.